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**TEACHERS' COMPETENCY AND LEARNERS' PERFORMANCE IN ENGLISH
OF GRADE 2 PUPILS: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION SCHEME**

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In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for
the Degree of Master of Arts in Education
Major in Administration and Supervision

by

ROSE ANN S. TOSTON

2021

UJER PERMISSION PAGE

TEACHERS' COMPETENCY AND LEARNERS' PERFORMANCE IN ENGLISH OF GRADE 2 PUPILS: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION SCHEME

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ABSTRACT

Title: TEACHERS' COMPETENCY AND LEARNERS' PERFORMANCE IN ENGLISH OF GRADE 2 PUPILS: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION SCHEME

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Degree: Master of Arts in Education major in Administration and Supervision

Year: 2021

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Rationale of the Study

Teachers, who are the most important factor of education, have the great task of inculcating to the learners the knowledge, skill and behavior needed in facing the everchanging society. Thus, the teachers' task to transmit knowledge requires them to be a highly competent learning facilitators while remaining as a role model soaring with moral integrity. This means that a school must not only have educationally qualified teachers but teachers who are truly dedicated and committed to serve the public specially the learners entrusted to their care.

This study is focused to determine teachers' competency and learners' performance in English of grade two teachers in Manila particularly in District V. Likewise, the benefits derived from the study hope to provide a springboard to design an intervention scheme towards gearing effort into improving the quality education.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to assess the teachers' competency and learners' performance in English of grade 2 pupils in public elementary schools in District V in the Division of Manila which served as basis to develop a proposed intervention scheme.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the professional profile of the teachers in handling Grade 2 learners in terms of:

- 1.1 Qualifications;
- 1.2 Training;
- 1.3 Length of service; and
- 1.4 Educational qualifications?

2. What is the level of teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers themselves in terms of:

- 2.1 Classroom management;
- 2.2 Mastery of the subjects;
- 2.3 Instructional material development;
- 2.4 Teaching strategies and approaches;
- 2.5 Communication skills;
- 2.6 Learning assessment and reporting; and
- 2.7 Community linkages?

3. Is there any significant difference in the assessment of the respondents of the above-mentioned variables?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' competency and professional profile?
5. What is the performance of the learners in English based on Phil-IRI result?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' competency and learners' performance?
7. What are the problems encountered by the respondents?
8. Based on the findings, what intervention scheme may be offered for implementation?

Research Method Used

This study utilized the descriptive and correlational method of research with questionnaires as the instrument in assessing the teachers' competency and learners' performance of grade two pupils. J. Nelson (2015) stated that as widely accepted, the descriptive method of research is a factfinding study that involves adequate and accurate interpretation of findings. The aim of this method is to provide the researcher with a profile or to describe the relevant aspects of the phenomenon from an individual, organizational or other perspective. Meanwhile, Heppner (2018), explained that correlational method examines the relationship between two or more variables. It is used in a wide array of studies that intend to determine and assess consistency and predictions among variables.

Relatively, descriptive, and correlational methods are appropriate to this study since it attempted to describe the competency of teachers through the assessment of different variables related to competency of the respondents and

assess relationship between teachers' competency and learners' performance. It also identified the problems encountered by the respondents which served as basis for the proposed intervention scheme.

Research Locale

This was conducted in the Division City Schools of Manila for the school year 2018-2019.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents were composed of (9) School Heads, (31) Master Teachers, and (100) Teachers in the selected public elementary schools in the Division City Schools of Manila.

Instrumentation

The study will utilize the following instrument in gathering the needed data:

1. Survey Questionnaire

The primary gathering tool for the data of this study. The items in the questionnaire are used to solicit information needed on the assessment of the given variables under study. This said instrument was consist of three (3) parts. **Part I.** Demographic Profile of the respondents. This generate data on gender, age, civil status, educational attainment and length of service. **Part I.** Demographic Profile of the respondents. This generate data on gender, age, civil status, educational attainment and length of service. **Part II.** Assessment of the teachers' competency such as classroom management; mastery of the subjects; instructional material development; teaching strategies and approaches;

communication skills; learning assessment and reporting and community linkages. **Part III.** Problem encountered by teachers teaching grade two pupils. Each item was rated by the respondents using a five (5) point Likert scale.

2. Documentary Analysis

This was used to look into the performance of the grade two learners in Reading as per record presented by the school authority.

Statistical Tools Used

The following statistical tools were exploited to analyze the result of the study.

1. **Percentage.** This will be used as descriptive statistics or something that describes a part of a whole.
2. **Frequency.** It is the actual response to a specific item/question in the questionnaire where the respondent ticks his choice.
3. **Ranking.** This will be used to reinforce the percentage to show the proportional importance of an item considered.
4. **Weighted Mean.** This was used to get the average frequency of the responses in each weighted item.
5. **Standard Deviation.** This was used to tell how measurement for are spread out from the average (mean), or expected value.
6. **Analysis of Variance (F-Test).** This was used to answer the significant relationship of teachers' competencies; to compare the responses of the three group of respondents and to accept or reject the hypothesis of the study.
7. **Pearson r.** This was used to determine whether significant relationship exist between variables.

Summary

The following are the findings of the specific problems drawn from the study:

1. **On the professional profile of the teachers handling Grade 2 learners.** The overall qualifications of the respondents are 30 or 21.43 percent PBET passer; and 110 or 78.57 percent LET passer. For Trainings there are 29 or 20.71 percent who attended international level; 49 or 35.00 percent national level; 11 or 7.86 percent regional level; 41 or 29.29 percent division level; 10 or 7.14 percent district level and there is none for school level. For years in service, 66 or 47.14 percent respondents are more than 10 years in service; 42 or 30.00 percent are 6-10 years; 26 or 18.57 percent are 1-5 years; 6 or 4.29 percent are less than 1 year in service. For educational attainment, 65 or 46.43 percent have bachelor's degree; 60 or 42.86 percent are masters with units; 9 or 6.43 percent have master's degree; and 3 or 2.14 percent are both doctorate with units; and doctorate degree.

2. **On the level of teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers themselves.** The overall assessment on the training needs of teachers are as follows: communication skills rated as Highly Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.20 as rank 1; mastery of the subjects rated as Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.17 as rank 2; classroom management; and learning assessment and reporting with both rated as Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.16 as rank 3 and 4; community linkages rated as Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.13 as rank 5; instructional material development rated as Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.12 as rank 6; and teaching strategies and approaches rated as Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.07 as rank 7.

3. On a significant difference in the assessment of the respondents of the abovementioned variables. As manifested, the computed F-values are as follows: mastery of subject (6.14656); instructional materials development (13.0265); teaching strategies and approaches (24.0035); communication skills (8.60454); learning assessment and reporting (8.12013); and community linkages (13.2263) were all higher than the critical value of 3.00 with 2 and 137 degree of freedom with 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there are significant differences on the teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, the computed F-value in classroom management which is 1.73277 which is lower than the critical values of 3.00 with 2 and 137 with the degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance with 2 and 137. Hence, there is no significant difference on the teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

4. On a significant relationship between the teachers' competency and professional profile? As revealed in the computed t-values are: classroom management (64.36); mastery of the subjects (54.62); instructional material development (94.76); teaching strategies and approaches (47.88); communication skills (54.51); learning assessment and reporting (46.65); and community linkages (64.72) were all higher than the critical values of 1.943 at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 16. Hence, there is significant relationship between the teachers' competency and professional profile. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

5. On the performance of the learners in English based on Phil-IRI result? As reflected from the documentary analysis, on the learner's performance based on the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory result, the level

of reading comprehension, are as follows: for the Academic Year 2016-2017, frustration have 1165 or 18.87 percent; instructional have 1392 or 22.55 percent; independent have 1878 or 30.42 percent; and non-reader have 1738 or 28.15 percent with a verbal interpretation of good. For the Academic Year 2017-2018, frustration have 1520 or 31.18 percent; instructional have 1010 or 20.72 percent; independent have 603 or 12.37 percent; and non-reader have 1742 or 35.73 percent with a verbal interpretation of average. For the Academic Year 2018-2019, frustration have 1118 or 27.16 percent; instructional have 882 or 21.43 percent; independent have 539 or 13.10 percent; and nonreader have 1577 or 38.31 percent with a verbal interpretation of average.

6. On a significant relationship between the teachers' competency and learners' performance. As revealed in Table 24, the computed t-values are: classroom management (14.74); mastery of the subjects (13.42); instructional material development (12.41); teaching strategies and approaches (11.55); communication skills (13.35); learning assessment and reporting (13.04); and community linkages (12.47) were all higher than the critical values of 1.943 at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 6. Hence, there is significant relationship between the teachers' proficiency and learner's performance – non-readers. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

7. On problems encountered by the respondents. The assessment of the problems encountered on the teachers' competency rated as Least Encountered with overall weighted mean of 2.49. It has been identified as the top ranked among the problems encountered such as poor attendance and study habits of learners; lack of teachers' skills; lack of parents / community cooperation; lack of sufficient time in teaching; lack of learners' proper nutrition

resulting to poor focus; lack of textbooks and other instructional supplies; lack of facilities for conducive teaching and learning process; lack of support from higher school officials; and lack of knowledge on the use of ICT.

8. On the findings of the study. The proposed intervention scheme of teachers has been designed and developed to continuously enhance and much more competent of teachers in teaching English subject.

Conclusions

In the lights of the foregoing finding of the study, the following conclusion are drawn:

1. The professional profile of the teachers handling Grade 2 learners are licensed, well-trained, competent teachers and qualified and equipped with a basic knowledge and skills to teach the learners.
2. The competency of teachers in teaching English for grade 2 learners assessed by the respondents is Competent.
3. There is no significant difference on the teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.
4. There is a direct relationship between the teachers' competency and professional profile. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.
5. The performance of the learners in English based on Phil-IRI result for the Academic Year 2016-2017 is Good, for the Academic Year 2017-2018 is Average and for the Academic Year 2018-2019 is Average.
6. There is a direct relationship between the teachers' proficiency and learner's performance in Phil-IRI. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.
7. The problems encountered relative to teachers' proficiency in teaching English rated as Least Encountered.

8. The proposed intervention scheme of teachers has been designed and developed to continuously enhance competent of teachers in teaching English subject.

Recommendation

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented for consideration.

1. The school administrators must ensure that there is a sustainable and continuous development of instructional competence of teachers.
2. The teacher must undergo intensive service training and seminar workshop in teaching methodologies and strategies to expedite the transfer of knowledge and skills to the learners.
3. Sustained the evaluation skills to get the accurate feedbacks on the academic performance of the learners.
4. The problems encountered must be addressed immediately and promptly and taking action needed to enhance the teaching competency of the teachers.
5. Adopt intervention scheme to provide based line of information for policy formulation to access and correct the weaknesses of the teachers concern.
6. Conduct parallel study to discover other variables or areas which are not cover with the framework of the present study.

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DEDICATION

This study is wholeheartedly dedicated to my parents; who have been my source of inspiration and gave me strength in times of giving up, who continually provided moral, spiritual, emotional and financial support.

To my ever supportive and knowledgeable Thesis adviser, Dr. Eledio T. Acibar, who shared his expertise and guidance to finish this study.

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Thank you for the strength, power of mind, protection, skills and for giving a healthy life.

All of these I offer to you.

R. A. S. T.

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CHAPTER 1

The Problem and Its Background

Introduction

In our society where learning is paramount, ensuring quality education is not just a new predicament. Basically, the Philippines viewed education as seemingly a prerequisite to social and economic success. Thus, the Department of Education (DepEd) launched various innovation and strategies to foster our country's poor-quality education. However, despite of the effort of our government in achieving this goal, still our country is far beyond global standard.

Every time there are mishaps and impediments in education the concern always boils down to the main service provider of education- the teacher. Teachers are considered the center to the provision of quality education. They are expected to continually adapt to meet evolving learners' needs and guarantee their optimum learning experiences in a caring, respectful, safe inclusive learning environment.

Today, teachers' competency are measured by their many commitments. Their commitments to teaching, to learners, to the school, to DepEd programs, project of the government and to the community are some of the determining factors for them to be recognized as competent and proficient educators.

Also, Teachers' competency have a very strong positive relationship with the learners' academic performance. Competent teachers must not only possess the ability to impart knowledge, practical skills or understanding to its learners but most importantly, they must always find new ways to stimulate learners' interest since quality of learners would be a reflection of what kind of society we had.

For the past years, learners' performance particularly in reading are closely monitored. Several tools were designed to assess and measure

teachers' competency in teaching reading. One of these tools is the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). Phil-IRI is designed to determine the individual learner's performance in oral and silent reading as well as listening comprehension. It is anchored on the flagship program of DepEd: "Every Child a Reader Program" which aims to ensure that every Filipino child become a good reader.

The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) is an informal reading inventory consist of graded passages designed to assesses the individual student's performance and determine their reading level as to independent, instructional and frustration. The results of the assessment can be used to conceptualize group or individual instruction appropriate to the students' needs, skills, and abilities. The Phil-IRI data may also be used as bases in planning the reading instruction of the teachers and the school's reading programs or activities to improve the overall school's reading performance.

In response to this poor learners' performance based on the result of the Phil-IRI, different service training sessions were conducted, seminars and symposia were held which aimed to update the content knowledge of English teachers in grade two based from the competency outlined in the K-12 curriculum.

Although, poor quality education may be attributed to various factors such as poor school facilities, big class size, environmental influence and family problem among others. Nevertheless, it is always believed that the overall academic performance of every learners depend mainly on how competent the teacher is as a classroom facilitators.

Teachers, who are the most important factor of education, have the great task of inculcating to the learners the knowledge, skill and behavior needed in facing the ever-changing society. Thus, the teachers' task to transmit knowledge requires them to be a highly competent learning

facilitators while remaining as a role model soaring with moral integrity. This means that a school must not only have educationally qualified teachers but teachers who are truly dedicated and committed to serve the public specially the learners entrusted to their care.

This study is focused to determine teachers' competency and learners' performance in English of grade two teachers in Manila particularly in District V. Likewise, the benefits derived from the study hope to provide a springboard to design an intervention scheme towards gearing effort into improving the quality education.

Theoretical Framework

The current study is anchored from the competency framework for teacher according to Goodwill (2017) which articulates the complex nature of teaching by describing three professional elements of teachers work; attributes, practice and knowledge. This element of works was interrelated by the way as they are put practice in the classroom.

This expresses competency standard of teachers working within the Western Australian Government Schools. Competency standards outline the varying degree of effectiveness of teachers that demonstrate when applying knowledge, skills and attitude to their specific teaching context by providing explicit standards that will guide teachers in their work to improve student's level of educational achievement, the Framework is a valuable tool for increasing public confidence in public school educational system. It familiarizes that the teaching profession requires teacher to be a lifelong learner who engage in on-going professional learning.

It recognized that teachers are highly dedicated and strive to improve outcomes for their learners. Professional learning is seen as key inputs of ensuring that teachers have the skills, with high quality education during the course of their career.

This theory mentioned is applicable to the present study with the end view of the fact that deals with competency level of teachers teaching English in grade 2 which correlates to the academic performance of the learners. Furthermore. The instructional competency level of teachers would precisely affect the performance of the learners in the quest for quality education as the primordial consideration to attend the goal and objective of the English program in the basic education setting.

Conceptual Framework

This study utilized the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model which served as the basis in the conduct of the investigation.

The **INPUT** (I) of the research includes the demographic profile of the respondents such as gender, age, civil status, educational attainment and length of service, survey result on teaching competency, Phil-IRI Result, references such as books, journals, thesis/ dissertation and online sources.

The **PROCESS** (P) of the research entails the development of survey questionnaires, assessment of teachers' competencies on the variable understudy such as classroom management, mastery of the subjects, instructional material development, teaching strategies and approaches, communication skills, learning assessment and reporting, community linkages, statistical treatment of data and analysis and interpretation of gathered data

The **OUTPUT** (O) of the study is a proposed intervention scheme.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to assess the teachers' competency and learners' performance in English of grade 2 pupils in public elementary schools in District V in the Division of Manila which served as basis to develop a proposed intervention scheme.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the professional profile of the teachers in handling Grade 2 learners in terms of:
 - 1.1 Qualifications;
 - 1.2 Training;
 - 1.3 Length of service; and
 - 1.4 Educational qualifications?
2. What is the level of teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers themselves in terms of:
 - 2.1 Classroom management;
 - 2.2 Mastery of the subjects;
 - 2.3 Instructional material development;
 - 2.4 Teaching strategies and approaches;
 - 2.5 Communication skills; and
 - 2.6 Learning assessment and reporting;
 - 2.7 Community linkages?
3. Is there any significant difference in the assessment of the respondents of the above-mentioned variables?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' competency and professional profile?
5. What is the performance of the learners in English based on Phil-IRI result?

6. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' competency and learners' performance?
7. What are the problems encountered by the respondents?
8. Based on the findings, what intervention scheme may be offered for implementation?

Hypothesis

The hypotheses of the study are:

1. There is no significant difference among the assessment of the three groups of respondents in terms of classroom management, mastery of the subjects, instructional material development, teaching strategies and approaches, communication skills, learning assessment and reporting and community linkages.
2. There is no significant relationship between the teacher competencies and professional profile.
3. There is no significant relationship between teachers' competency and learners' performance.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study dealt primarily between the teachers' competency and learners' performance level in English of grade 2 pupils in public elementary schools in District V in the Division of Manila for the school year 2018-2019 in terms of classroom management; mastery of the subjects; instructional material development; teaching strategies and approaches; communication skills; learning assessment and reporting and community linkages. Learners Phil-IRI results in English for the past three (3) years. The respondents of the study were 9 school heads, 31 master teachers and 100 grade two teachers in District V in the Division of Manila. The school which participated in the study were Margarita Roxas de Ayala Elementary School, Rafael Palma

Elementary School, Fernando Ma. Guerrero Elementary School, Epifanio delos Reyes Elementary School, Silahis ng Katarungan Special School, Justo Lukban Elementary School, Aurora A. Quezon Elementary School, Dr. Celedonio A. Salvador Elementary School, Benigno Aquino Elementary School and H. J. Atienza Elementary School. The study was conducted from November 2018 to November 2019.

Significance of the Study

The results of this study may prove beneficial to the following:

Learners The findings of this study is an instrument to provide them real quality education, enhance their skills, talents and abilities through having effective and efficient teachers' performance rooted from the higher or improved teachers' competency.

Teachers The result obtained from this study would help teachers to evaluate themselves and realize the importance of developing high level of teaching competency that would later increase students' academic performance.

School Administrators The findings of this study may help them to crystalize the instructional deficiencies of teachers teaching education program to meet the standard requirement set by the DepEd as expected. Also, it may serve as basis for policy formulation to improve instructional leadership of the teachers in order to enhance quality instruction beneficial to the interest of the learners.

Parents This study may enhance the quality of imposed study habit on their children and may help them identify their children's' needs and weaknesses. Thus, it can produce support and acceptance of their child's skills and capabilities.

Future Researchers This study and its results may give insights; a readily accessible database of information on the teachers' competency and

the areas investigated herein may give the student researcher the impetus to make further or related studies. This may also lead to further enhancements on the teachers' competency and in developing new training or model that would help teachers to improve learners' academic achievement and school performance as a whole.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined operationally and lexically to provide a common frame of reference.

Classroom Management. Refers to the administration or direction of activities with special reference to such problems as discipline, democratic techniques, use of supplies and materials and physical features of the classroom as well as social relationship of students.

Communication Skills. Refers to the skills of teacher which involves presenting, explaining, demonstrating, etc. so that the subject matter is transmitted effectively to pupils and becomes part of their knowledge.

Curriculum Content and Pedagogy. Refers to the elements of the teaching-learning process that work in convergence to help students understand the curricular goals and objectives, and to attain high standards of learning defined in the curriculum.

Instructional Materials. Refers to the teachers' knowledge in developing different types of teaching aids available, their place in the teaching-learning process and the methods of their evaluation.

Intervention Scheme. Refers to the program design to enhance the teachers' skills and knowledge through attending seminars and workshop to become proficient in their own field of specialization in the course of their career.

Learners' Performance. Refers to the result of the Phil-IRI of district five schools from the Division office for the last three years.

Learning Environment. Refers to the classroom or outside the school where students feel safe, comfortable and feel that they are cared for while acquiring knowledge and skills.

Mastery of the Subject Matter. Refers to the teacher's knowledge which entails helping others learn, then understanding what is to be taught as well as the process of selecting worthwhile learning activities, giving helpful explanation, asking productive questions and evaluating students' learning.

Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). Refers to the assessment designed to determine the individual learner's performance in oral and silent reading as well as listening comprehension.

Professional Growth and Development. Refers to the wide variety of specialized training, formal education, or advanced professional learning intended to help administrators, teachers and other educators improve their professional knowledge, competence, skills and effectiveness.

Planning, Assessing & Reporting. Refers to the alignment of assessment and planning activities. In particular, the domain focuses on the use of assessment to plan and revise teaching-learning materials.

School Community Linkages. Refers to the one responsible for creating a shared vision for the school, identifying the work of partner with the school.

Teachers' Competency. Refers to the ability of individual to think for themselves as an expression of moral and intellectual maturity, and to take responsibility for their learning and for their actions.

CHAPTER 2

Review of Related Literature and Studies

Local Literature

The school system in the Philippines is considered as the main instrument to determine the quality of education in our country. It is where the achievement of our educational goal and objectives are measured. It is an institution where formal teaching-learning process takes and exist primarily for the welfare of the learners.

Likewise, Llego (2019) believed that teacher plays a vital part in ensuring the quality of teaching and learning process. Effective teachers are necessary to improve learner's academic performance. Hence, enhancing teacher quality ranks foremost in many educational reform efforts toward quality education.

In addition, Bilbao (2015) identified teacher as an extraordinary person in whose hands lie `the future of the country. Thus, a teacher must become globally competent who possesses qualities, skills, knowledge, views, with wider breadth and deeper sense so they could cater the 21st century learners more effectively.

Giron (2016) mentioned that the realities of our modern world require a different kind of teacher and a K to 12 teachers must possess the 5C's to be effective. These are character, commitment, competence, creativity, and compassion. These qualities are necessary to produce graduates who are holistically developed with the 21st century skills prepared for higher education.

Moreover, Farrel (2016) quoted that with the greater diversity and the new demands on education systems, the importance of validated, effective, and responsive teaching strategies became the highlights of every research conducted by the educational practitioners, leaders and policy makers.

Recognizes the vital role of teachers in nation-building and development through a responsible and literate citizenry. The Department of Education implemented the Republic Act 7836: Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994 which ensure and promote quality education by proper supervision and regulation of the licensure examination and professionalization of the practice of the teaching profession.

According to Guinayen (2016) Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) is a test of the overall knowledge and proficiency of prospective teachers to provide a reliable structure, which the practice of prospective teachers can be measured and proven, and it gives access to continuing growth and development. Licensing is required to ensure that the only qualified teachers can be hired specifically in public school.

However, taking Licensure Examination for Teachers requires basic qualification. This includes undergraduate degrees in Education, such as Bachelor of Elementary Education, Bachelor of Secondary Education, and Bachelor of Early Childhood Education, and their respective equivalents. Aspiring educators with a bachelor's in a subject other than teaching earn a master's in teaching or undergo alternative teacher certification. Master's in education degrees may help practicing teachers learn new skills and qualify for a raise or promotion reason why more and more teachers are pursuing higher level of education such as doctorate degree.

Noticeably, every country has designed its own standard to measure competency of teacher. Thus, to respond to this demand from the field, the Department of Education Secretary Leonor M. Briones signed a package of policy reforms that seeks to improve our quality of education, the Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers (PPST), through DepEd Order no. 42, s. 2017.

Based on the Basic Education Sector Transformation (2018), PPST is a new standard, which build on the previously-adopted National

Competency-based Teacher Standards (NCBTS). It defines what competency constitute teacher quality both in pre-service and in-service education and in the context of k to 12 reform. Furthermore, PPST has a distinct domains, strands and indicators that provide measures of professional learning, competent skill, and effective teaching practice.

The Department of Education also quoted that the PPST highlights the required skills and competency of quality teachers, helping them to cope with the emerging global context. Moreover, if these required skills are not met by the teacher, the PPST offers professional development intervention that helps assure parents and guardians that their children receive quality basic education from qualified professional whose competency are abreast with changes and advancement in the information age.

The launched of DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, otherwise known as National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers (PPST) brought about the introduction of the revised guidelines for the Result-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). As stipulated in the DepEd Order No. 2 s. 2015, RPMS is an organization-wide process that ensures employees' focus on work efforts toward achieving the DepEd vision, mission and values. It serves as a tool to manage, monitor and measure performance and identify human resource and organizational development needs to enable continues work improvement and individual growth.

Anchored on the domains present in the PPST-RPMS manual, similar factors were used to assess the teachers' proficiency in teaching such as: Classroom management; Mastery of the subjects; Instructional material development; Teaching strategies and approaches; Communication skills; Learning assessment and reporting; and Community linkages.

Salandanan (2012) stated that the quality of education depends primarily upon the quality of teachers. The competency of teacher in terms of

knowledge of the subject matter and skills in teaching methodologies spell success in the teaching profession. A teacher should be able to feed the minds of the learners with an advance and deeper understanding of the lesson accurately and confidently.

Foreign Literature

Also, Davies (2021) added that enhancing teaching strategies and approaches is a life-long learning process as an educator. Teachers always have the potential to progress and refine their skills through seminars and workshops. Furthermore, trainings provide variety of activities and practices that meet the needs of the teachers. It helps to improve their teaching methods, classroom management, professional growth and development and knowledge and skills enhancement that leads to the upliftment of student-centered learning. As they always say, quality teachers produce quality learners.

Lastly, as mentioned by Epstein (2019) building community linkages is now part of an effective teaching, Community involvement must focus on engaging all families in ways that improve the school climate and promote academic and behavioral results for students. Goal-linked family and community engagement activities help improve student attendance, achievement, behavior, and other indicators of success in school. Likewise, it is also a way to generate resources that are essential for effective instruction. When such resources are appropriately channeled, they can support innovative educational programs that meet the learning needs of increasingly diverse learner populations and promote equity in the educational opportunities available to all students.

Meanwhile, Uzzo, Graves, Shay, Harford and Thompson (2018) explained that mastery of the subject is the ability of the teacher to teach and explain the subject matter well in such a way that students will be easily grasp its content. Teachers with the good knowledge on variety of strategies and

technique in teaching is able to plan lesson by way of highlighting the main points of the lesson with clarity of the knowledge content. Mastery of the subject matter recognize the melding of subject matter expertise with pedagogical strategies and knowledge of the learners to produce high-quality classroom practice that enable learners to explore knowledge through interactive participation and hands-on experiences. It allows teacher to consider the structure and importance of instructional topic, recognize the differences that will make it more or less appropriate to learners, and justify the selection of teaching practices based on the student abilities and skills.

Young and Travis (2018) believed on the importance of communication skills in teaching for it represent your thought process, academic background, social skills, and cultural views. Accordingly, effective communication through the use of a chosen language implies good or pleasant speech and this turn requires not only a clear, well-modulated voice but also speech that is easily understood and is accurate in the production of the individual sounds and in the selection of words. Good skills and solid choices in the use of language can help learners better understand the knowledge imparted.

Relatively, Unal (2016) stated that years of experience affect teachers' classroom management approaches. Experienced teachers are believed to have combined years of service and a repertoire of classroom skills and strategies. They typically can prioritize tasks and to attend selectively to a number of key classroom matters. They generally can manage the dynamic nature of a classroom setting and to deal effectively with the most salient aspect of a classroom—unpredictability. Compared to beginning teachers, experienced teachers tend to be less hesitant and more flexible and adaptable. In addition, beginning teachers are sometimes less able to work with speed, fluidity, and flexibility or to have mental models that permit large amounts of information to be accessed and handled effectively. According to

the literature, it takes between four and seven years of experience for an individual to develop into a competent teacher

Likewise, Tripathi (2016) discussed the role of teaching strategies and approaches. He said that the primary task of the teacher is to bring desired behavioral changes in the student to make it practical in order to solve a real-life time situation. This can be achieved by transforming the learning environment from teacher-centered to learner-centered. In modern education, the demand in designing innovative teaching strategies to meet the needs of today's diverse technological learners continue to grow.

In the same context, Klenowski and Smith (2014) talked about the important part of Learning assessment and reporting in ensuring quality education. According to them, these domains are crucial in identifying the strengths and weaknesses not only of the learners and teachers but as well as the curriculum system to enable to determine the appropriate action to be taken in the future. For teachers to be effective, they must have a repertoire of skills and understanding to design quality assessment and to use achievement standard and evidence as a means to discern, monitor and improve learning as well as judge the qualities of student work. Assessment and reporting must be a shared enterprise, with benefits accruing to all students, including those who are marginalized and disengaged and those who are identified as gifted and talented.

According to Young (2014) classroom management is one of the most important factors affecting student learning. Simply put, students learn better when they view the learning environment as positive and supportive. A positive classroom environment is one in which students feel a sense of belongingness, trust others, and feel encourages to tackle challenges, take risk without exposing to any form of violence. Such an environment provides established routines, relevant content, clear learning goals and feedback, opportunities to build social skills, and strategies to help students succeed.

Additionally, Zeiger (2010) described instructional material development as factor in assessing teachers' proficiency. Teachers must be capable of designing instructional materials to meet student needs and cover the standard. This require knowing how to choose and create instructional materials to accommodate students at different level and employ varied teaching strategies, best practices and other appropriate teaching approaches which allow competent teachers to effectively teach the content of the curriculum.

Local Studies

The following studies were conducted to determine the relationship of teacher's proficiency to the academic performance of learners.

The study of Torres (2017) it was revealed that found that reading is considered an encounter and an prospect to every person's daily activities. If its ultimate aim is to develop critical thinking, then, it has to be inculcated in the basic education. Observably, there is a prevailing issue on the low performance of students in content areas owing to their lack of comprehension it is therefore the purpose of this study to determine how the teachers instructional competence influences the intermediate of the students comprehension skills as well as their critical thinking ability. Utilizing the normative-evaluated method, findings revealed that the intermediate students obtained an above average performance in the following directions. This reveals that the students are generally obedient. They are conscious of applying the skills in carrying out their varied activities/ responsibilities because according to them careful compliance to standard and the like, engenders peace and order.

In the study conducted by Tilan (2017) she stated how teachers' competency is related to pupils' achievement in English. According to her, a teacher who possesses background knowledge of basic-principles, concept, rules and regulations relating to the subject matter contributes to increased

pupils' achievement. The result of her study showed that pupils' perceive their teachers "Often" manifest the competence in teaching. The level of the respondents' achievement is found to be on the average level as indicated in their obtained grades in the corresponding subjects English, Science and Technology and Mathematics which is equivalent to 80-84. Overall, all subject concerned have significant correlation whether at 0.01 or 0.05 level and the correlation made were interpreted as negligible correlations.

On the study of Pulgo (2017) on the relationship of teachers' competencies and performance it was shown that there was no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the extent of importance of teachers' competencies. This entailed that qualifications plays a minor role in assessing whether the teacher is highly competent.

Similar study was done by Ocampo (2016) he found out that across Mindanao City Division pupils who do not possess acceptable reading ability experience frustration every time they are engaged in reading activities, such that they lag in their academic achievement which is evident in their National Achievement Test (NAT) results. One of the factors that attributed to influence pupils' learning is the teachers' capability and competence in teaching. While there is no significant relationship was noted between the teachers' level of teaching competence and the students' academic achievement as well as between the teachers' personality traits and students' academic performance. However, teaching competence of teachers is significantly related to their personality traits.

Meanwhile, Bilasa (2016) determined the effects of teaching competencies and its relation to academic performance of selected grade 10 students in MAPEH of San Isidro National High school S.Y. 2015-2016. The result of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between the teacher competencies and academic performance of the students. It is

recommended that teacher should be provided with technical assistance, training, and seminars in the classroom management, use of instructional materials and use of appropriate instructional method to help improve the academic performance of students.

Likewise, Andaya (2016) added individual factors and instructional factors as predictors of academic performance of respondents. This concluded that academic performance is affected by the students themselves and the teacher. The teacher who is at the center stage of instruction really plays a major role in the learning of students. The success or failure of students in school and life greatly lies on the hand of the teacher. Findings identified that teachers' competence on teaching-learning instruction has a strong correlation with students' academic performance with coefficient of correlation values of 0.80 for the three school years. Also, students' academic performance has a very strong significant relation with the teachers' competence on students' outcome, it has strong significant relation with teaching-learning instruction, personal and professional attributes, good and ethical governance, and competitiveness.

Apura (2016) revealed in her study about the relationship of teaching competence of secondary teachers and academic performance. The study utilized the NCBTS 7 domains as determinants for teaching competence. Result shown that the respondents were highly competent on the five domains namely: socio regard for learning, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum, and planning assessing and reporting. They were very highly competent in community linkages and personal, social growth and professional development. Furthermore, the study concluded that there is significant relationship between teaching competence of teachers and students' academic performance. The result served as basis in formulation of a proposed professional training program.

Hence, Fernandez (2015) revealed that there was a significant relationship that exist between teachers' pedagogical competent and pupils, academic performance. Very highly competent teachers tend to have pupils with proficient academic performance, those highly competent and competent tend to have pupils with approaching proficiency academic performance.

Foreign Studies

Rabo (2018) study centers mainly on the relationship between teachers' competence, school climate and students' academic performance. The study revealed that teacher composure, good knowledge of subject matter and teacher/student relationship enhances academic performance of learners. Furthermore, a positive school climate enhances good academic performance: which include school culture, classroom ecology, school physical plant and school administration. That provide conducive and enabling environment for teaching and learning activities, which enhances academic performance.

Teygong, Moses & Daniel (2017) also believed that teachers have important influence on learner' academic achievement. Their study found out that teachers utilized question and answer method, problem solving and demonstration as main method of teaching. The findings meant that teacher who used various teaching method and exceptional teaching competence were able to post positive result in their classes than those who relied on one method of teaching. Due to this, a cross-sectional study of questionnaire survey research design was conducted in this respect. Data on teaching qualification, characteristics and competence were generated from the target respondents. The questionnaires were distributed through email and, dro-off and pick procedures. Overall, findings from the testing of hypothesis indicate that there is a significant relationship between teachers' qualification and students' performance.

Brokamp, Houtveen & Van de Grift (2017) study the relationship among students' reading performance, their behavior (task-focused behavior, emotional stability, and complaint behavior) in the classroom, and the teacher's skills in third grade classroom. Result from this study showed that students' reading performance and teachers' skills are all significantly interrelated. The teacher can improve the behavior of the students by providing high-quality reading instruction. Better behavior at the beginning of the school year goes with better reading performance at the end of the school year.

Buddin & Zammaro (2016) posited that teacher effectiveness is typically measured by traditional teacher qualification standard, such as experience, education, and scores on licensure examination. RAND researcher found no evidence that these standards have a substantial effect on student achievement. Alternative measures of teacher qualification and different kinds of reward systems might be more effective at improving teacher quality.

Kusumi (2015) made a comparative study on the relationship of teacher's proficiency and students' performance in English language learning in some urban and rural schools of Republic of Kosovo. His study was conducted an empirical research regarding student performance based on the four language skills such as reading, writing, speaking and listening. The result derived from his study as seen in the performance of students in English language was that there is a significant relationship between students from urban location who got better performance than students from rural. This is due to the teachers' experience and education as the teacher in urban location are statistically more educated and proficient.

Kaur and Talwar (2015) designed a study to examine the relationship between teaching competency and emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers. The findings of the study reveal a significant positive

relationship between teachers' teaching competency and their emotional intelligence. This is due to the reason that the success of teachers depends both on their emotional intelligence and teaching competency. Emotional intelligence has been an important factor in teaching learning process which demand teaching competency on the part of the teacher. Teacher who are emotionally balanced and intelligent have the capacity to generate new ideas and adopt new methods in teaching. However, insignificant difference is found between teaching competencies as well as between emotional intelligence of secondary school teachers teaching in public and private schools. The study also indicated that teaching competency and emotional intelligence are not influence by gender.

Bonney, Amoah, Micah, Ahiamenyo & Lemaire (2015) agreed that there are other factors that influence students' academic achievement. Herein they investigated the relationship between the quality teacher and students' academic performance in Sekondi Takoradi Metropolitan Assembly (STMA) Junior High School. The result of the study showed that even though the quality of teachers was high in terms of their academic and professional qualification, it did not reflect much in the performance of the students. Teachers' classroom effectiveness has been found to have only a minimal influence on the academic performance of pupils in public junior high school in STMA in the Western Region of Ghana.

Further, Wolf, (2014), described the characteristics of competent teachers' knowledge. Competent teachers' perceptions of student learning difficulties: feel accountable for problems with the student learning (for what they do/don't learn); believe they are capable of finding solutions to student learning problem; learning problems were related to lesson structure and organization. Conceptions of knowledge; showed willingness to learn; tried to identify important components and create steps when teaching new concepts; and relied on logical or technical explanations to justify lesson

content. Reflective Practice: recognized a range of student ability and knowledge; lessons were linked to continual student assessment (informal, subjective, and reflexive) and used appraisals to identify difficulties and find supporting activities; and made decisions for teaching activities based on subjective student performance observations.

Johansson, Myrberg and Rosen (2014) investigated the influence of teacher competence on third grade students reading achievement in public school in Sweden. Result showed that teacher education is of great importance and has a strong impact on students' reading achievement. The effectiveness of teachers have been shown to be closely connected to appropriate teacher education.

Synthesis

The preceding discussion on the related literatures and studies included in this research manifest a strong relevance to the topic being undertaken.

The information discussed by Salandanan (2012), Bilbao (2015), Giron (2016), Llego (2019) and Farrel (2016), Kusumi (2015), Johansson, Myrberg and Rosen (2014), Teygong, Moses & Daniel (2017), Brokamp, Houtveen & Van de Grift (2017), Rabo (2018), Kaur and Talwar (2014), Bonney, Amoah, Micah, Ahiamenyio & Lemaire (2015) and Buddin & Zammato (2016) highlighted the importance of effective teacher in improving learner's academic performance. According to them, if the teacher is proficient in teaching there is a greater chance the student will perform better in school. They investigated other factors that may also contribute to the teaching performance of teacher as well as the academic achievement of students in foreign context.

Young (2014), Uzzo, Graves, Shay, Harford and Thompson (2018), Zeiger (2010), Tripathi (2016), Young and Travis (2018), Klenowski and Smith (2014), and Epstein (2019), Tilan (2017), Ocampo (2016), Bilasa (2016), Andaya (2016), Apura (2016), Torres (2017), Fernandez (2015) and Pulgo (2017) revealed similar results regarding the relationship of teachers' proficiency/competency and students' academic performance. All of their studies proved that highly competent teachers tend to have pupils with high academic performance.

The cited review of literature and studies are particularly chosen since they do not parallel the present undertaking, but also help support the framework of the research process.

CHAPTER 3

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive and correlational method of research with questionnaires as the instrument in assessing the teachers' competency and learners' performance of grade two pupils. J. Nelson (2015) stated that as widely accepted, the descriptive method of research is a fact-finding study that involves adequate and accurate interpretation of findings. The aim of this method is to provide the researcher with a profile or to describe the relevant aspects of the phenomenon from an individual, organizational or other perspective. Meanwhile, Heppner (2018), explained that correlational method examines the relationship between two or more variables. It is used in a wide array of studies that intend to determine and assess consistency and predictions among variables.

Relatively, descriptive and correlational methods are appropriate to this study since it attempted to describe the competency of teachers through the assessment of different variables related to competency of the respondents and assess relationship between teachers' competency and learners' performance. It also identified the problems encountered by the respondents which served as basis for the proposed intervention scheme.

Population and Sampling

In this study, the researcher used purposive sampling, to select the population in which the sample will be taken. It is a sampling technique in which the units that are to be investigated are based on the judgment of the researcher. The population is focused on school administrators, master teachers and teachers from the public elementary schools in District V, Manila.

Table 1
Population of the Study

Type of Respondents	Population	Sample	Percentage
School Heads	9	9	100.00
Master Teachers	44	31	70.45
Teachers	136	100	73.53
Total	189	140	74.07

As presented in Table 1, respondents were School Heads with a frequency of 9 or 100.00 percent; Master teachers with 31 only out of 44 or 70.45 percent; and lastly, Teachers with 100 only out of 136 or 73.53 percent. The group of respondents with a total of 140 only out of 189 population.

Table 2
Respondents of the Study

Respondent	f	%
School Heads	9	6.43
Master Teachers	31	22.14
Teachers	100	71.43
Total	140	100.00

Table 2 presents the respondents of the study, among one hundred forty total respondents, it is divided into three groups of respondents, such as: 9 or 6.43 percent are school heads; 31 or 22.14 percent are master teachers; and 100 or 71.43 percent are teachers.

As illustrated by the data in table 3, there are 10 or 7.14 percent respondents from M. Roxas de Ayala ES; 18 or 12.86 percent respondents from R. Palma ES; 14 or 10.00 percent respondents from F. Ma. Guerrero ES; 16 or 11.43 percent respondents from E. Delos Reyes ES; 11 or 7.86 percent respondents from Sikat Special School; 15 or 10.71 percent respondents from J. Lukban ES; 20 or 14.29 percent respondents from A. A.

Table 3
Respondents of the Study as to School

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1. M. Roxas de Ayala ES	1	11.11	1	3.23	8	8.00	10	7.14
2. R. Palma ES	1	11.11	2	6.45	15	15.00	18	12.86
3. F. Ma. Guerrero ES	1	11.11	2	6.45	11	11.00	14	10.00
4. E. Delos Reyes ES	1	11.11	5	16.13	10	10.00	16	11.43
5. Sikat Special School	1	11.11	4	12.90	6	6.00	11	7.86
6. J. Lukban ES	1	11.11	4	12.90	10	10.00	15	10.71
7. A. Quezon ES	1	11.11	7	22.58	12	12.00	20	14.29
8. A. Salvador ES	1	11.11	4	12.90	6	6.00	11	7.86
9. A. Aquino ES	1	11.11	2	6.45	9	9.00	12	8.57
10. J. Atienza ES					13	13.00	13	9.29
Total	9	100.00	31	100.00	100	100.00	140	100.00

Quezon ES; 11 or 7.86 percent respondents from C. Salvador ES; 20 or 14.29 percent respondents from A. A. Quezon ES; 12 or 8.57 percent respondents from B. Aquino; 13 or 9.29 percent respondents from H. J. Atienza ES.

Table 4
Respondents as to Gender

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Male	4	44.44	4	12.980	2	2.00	10	7.14
Female	5	55.56	27	87.10	98	98.00	130	92.86
Total	9	100.00	31	100.00	100	100.00	140	100.00

Table 4 reflects the distribution of respondents as to gender such as: 130 or 92.86 percent are female; and 10 or 7.14 percent are male.

Table 5
Respondents as to Age Level

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
51 years old and above	7	77.78	14	45.16	9	9.00	30	21.43
46 – 50 years old	2	22.22	8	25.81	4	4.00	14	10.00
41 – 45 years old			1	3.23	10	10.00	11	7.86
36 – 40 years old			6	19.35	26	26.00	32	22.86
31 – 35 years old			2	6.45	23	23.00	25	17.86
26 – 30 years old					18	18.00	18	12.86
25 years old and below					10	10.00	10	7.14
Total	9	100.00	31	100.00	100	100.00	140	100.00

Table 5 manifests the distribution of respondents as to age level such as: 32 or 22.86 percent are aged 36-40 years old; 30 or 21.43 percent are aged 51 years old and above; 25 or 17.86 percent are aged 31-35 years old; 18 or 12.86 percent are aged 26-30 years old; 14 or 10 percent are aged 46-50 years old; 11 or 7.86 percent are aged 41-45 years old; and 10 or 7.14 percent are aged 25 years old and below.

Table 6
Respondents as to Civil Status

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Single	1	11.11	2	6.45	28	28.00	31	22.14
Married	8	88.89	23	74.19	68	68.00	99	70.71
Widow/er			6	19.35	4	4.00	10	7.14
Total	9	100.00	31	100.00	100	100.00	140	100.00

Table 6 displays the distribution of respondents as to civil status such as: 99 or 70.71 percent are married; 31 or 22.14 percent are single; and 10 or 7.14 percent are widow/er.

Research Instrument

The study will utilize the following instrument in gathering the needed data:

1. Survey Questionnaire

The primary gathering tool for the data of this study. The items in the questionnaire are used to solicit information needed on the assessment of the given variables under study. This said instrument was consist of three (3) parts. **Part I.** Demographic Profile of the respondents. This generate data on gender, age, civil status, educational attainment and length of service. **Part I.** Demographic Profile of the respondents. This generate data on gender, age, civil status, educational attainment and length of service. **Part II.** Assessment of the teachers' competency such as classroom management; mastery of the subjects; instructional material development; teaching strategies and approaches; communication skills; learning assessment and reporting and community linkages. **Part III.** Problem encountered by teachers teaching grade two pupils. Each item was rated by the respondents using a five (5) point Likert scale.

2. Documentary Analysis

This was used to look into the performance of the grade two learners in Reading as per record presented by the school authority.

Validation of the Research Instrument

After the researcher constructed the survey questionnaire it was submitted to the adviser for comments and corrections. After some revision,

it was validated by some experts who are not included in the study as respondents and was then again submitted to the adviser for final approval.

Data Gathering Procedures

The following procedures was taken by the researcher in the conduct of this study.

1. A permit was secured from office of the superintendent of the Division of manila to conduct a research study.

2. Upon approval of the request, the researcher begun to administer the survey questionnaire to the supposed respondents such as school heads and grade two teachers.

3 The distribution of the survey questionnaire was done personally by the researcher.

4. The survey questionnaire was collected, sorted, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted with the help of the statistician and the adviser.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were exploited to analyze the result of the study:

1. Frequency. It is the actual response to a specific item/question in the questionnaire where the respondent ticks his choice

2. Percentage. This was used as descriptive statistics or something that describes a part of a whole.

Formula:

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

Wherein: F = frequency

N = total number of respondents

3. Ranking. This was used to reinforce the percentage to show the proportional importance of an item considered.

4. Likert Scale. This was used to determine the descriptive rating of the proficiency of the respondents the following scale 5-point Likert scale was used.

1. The level of teaching competencies of grade two teachers in English.

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.20–5.00	Highly Competent	HC
4	3.40-4.19	Competent	C
3	2.60-3.39	Moderately Competent	MC
2	1.80-2.59	Least Competent	LC
1	1.00-1.79	Not Competent	NC

2. Problem Encountered relative to the competencies of grade two teachers in English.

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.20–5.00	Highly Encountered	HE
4	3.40-4.19	Encountered	E
3	2.60-3.39	Moderately Encountered	ME
2	1.80-2.59	Least Encountered	LE
1	1.00-1.79	Not Encountered	NE

5. Weighted Mean. This was used to get the average frequency of the responses in each weighted item.

Formula:

$$WM = \frac{TWR}{N}$$

Wherein: TWR = total weighted responses

N = number of responses

6. Standard Deviation. This was used to tell how measurement for are spread out from the average (mean), or expected value.

Formula:

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fd^2}{N} - \frac{(\sum fd)^2}{N}}$$

Wherein: $\sum fd$ = summation of the product and frequency and deviation

N = total number of respondents

SD = Standard Deviation

7. Analysis of Variance (F-test). This was used to answer the significant relationship of teachers' competencies; to compare the responses of the three group of respondents and to accept or reject the hypothesis of the study.

8. Pearson r. This was used to determine whether significant relationship exist between variables.

Formula:

$$R = \frac{N\sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{[N\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2][N\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

Wherein: X = sum of test x

Y = sum of test y

$\sum XY$ = sum of the product of x and y

$\sum X^2$ = sum of squared x scores

$\sum Y^2$ = sum of squared y scores

N = number of cases

CHAPTER 4

Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Sub-problem No. 1: What is the professional profile of the teachers handling Grade 2 learners in terms of:

1.1 Qualifications

Table 7
Respondents as to Qualifications

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
PBET Passer	7	77.78	14	45.16	9	9.00	30	21.43
LET Passer	2	22.22	17	54.84	91	91.00	110	78.57
Total	9	100.00	31	100.00	100	100.00	140	100.00

As denotes in Table 7, 30 or 21.43 percent of the respondents are PBET passer; and 110 or 78.57 percent are LET passer.

This can be inferred that licensing is required to ensure that the only qualified teachers can be hired specifically in public school. The Department of Education implemented the Republic Act 7836: Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994 which ensure and promote quality education by proper supervision and regulation of the licensure examination and professionalization of the practice of the teaching profession.

This is supported by the study of Guinayen (2016) accordingly, Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) is a test of the overall knowledge and proficiency of prospective teachers to provide a reliable structure, which the practice of prospective teachers can be measured and proven, and it gives access to continuing growth and development.

1.2 Trainings

Table 7
Respondents as to Trainings Attended

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
International Level	8	88.89	12	38.71	9	9.00	29	20.71
National Level	1	11.11	16	51.61	32	32.00	49	35.00
Regional Level			3	9.68	8	8.00	11	7.86
Division Level					41	41.00	41	29.29
District Level					10	10.00	10	7.14
School Level								
Total	9	100.00	31	100.00	100	100.00	140	100.00

Table 7 depicts the distribution of respondents as to trainings. Hence, 29 or 20.71 percent attended international level; 49 or 35.00 percent are national level; 11 or 7.86 percent are regional level; 41 or 29.29 percent are division level; 10 or 7.14 percent are district level and there is none for school level.

This can be inferred that teachers' training is important for both new teachers and veteran teachers. Life-long learning will keep teachers motivated and confidence to overcome any obstacles they face in the classroom.

According to Davies (2021) trainings provide variety of activities and practices that meet the needs of the teachers. It helps to improve their teaching methods, classroom management, professional growth and development and knowledge and skills enhancement that leads to the upliftment of student-centered learning. As they always say, quality teachers produce quality learners.

1.3 Length of Service

Table 8
Respondents as to Length of Service

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
More than 10 years	10	88.89	30	96.77	28	28.00	66	47.14
6-10 years	1	3.23	40	40.00	42	42.00	42	30.00
1-5 years					26	26.00	26	18.57
Less than 1 year					6	6.00	6	4.29
Total	9	100.00	31	100.00	100	100.00	140	100.00

As represented in Table 8, 66 or 47.14 percent respondents are more than 10 years in service; 42 or 30.00 percent are 6-10 years; 26 or 18.57 percent are 1-5 years; 6 or 4.29 percent are less than 1 year in service.

This can be inferred that length of service also plays a role in determining the teachers' competencies. It is believed that the greater the years of teachers in service the more they become competent on providing quality education.

This finding is linked to the study of Unal (2016) he stated that experienced teachers are believed to have combined years of service and a repertoire of classroom skills and strategies. They typically can prioritize tasks and to attend selectively to a number of key classroom matters. They generally can manage the dynamic nature of a classroom setting and to deal effectively with the most salient aspect of a classroom—unpredictability. Compared to beginning teachers, experienced teachers tend to be less hesitant and more flexible and adaptable. In addition, beginning teachers are sometimes less able to work with speed, fluidity, and flexibility or to have mental models that permit large amounts of information to be accessed and handled effectively. According to the literature, it takes between

four and seven years of experience for an individual to develop into a competent teacher.

1.4 Educational Qualifications

Table 9

Respondents as to Educational Qualifications

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Doctorate Degree	3	3.33					3	2.14
Doctorate with units			3	9.68			3	2.14
Master's Degree	3	33.33	4	12.90	2	2.00	9	6.43
Master's with units	3	33.33	24	77.42	33	33.00	60	42.86
Bachelor's Degree					65	65.00	65	46.43
Total	9	100.00	31	100.00	100	100.00	140	100.00

Table 9 depicts the distribution of respondents as to educational attainment such as: 65 or 46.43 percent have bachelor's degree; 60 or 42.86 percent are masters with units; 9 or 6.43 percent have master's degree; and 3 or 2.14 percent are both doctorate with units; and doctorate degree.

This can be inferred that for one to be qualified as a teacher. One must first possess basic qualification such as bachelor's degree. This is to ensure that the teacher is equip with basic knowledge and skills to teach the learners.

This is parallel to the qualifications presented in Republic Act 7836: Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994. Accordingly, taking Licensure Examination for Teachers requires basic qualification. This includes undergraduate degrees in Education, such as Bachelor of Elementary Education, Bachelor of Secondary Education, and Bachelor of Early Childhood Education, and their respective equivalents. Aspiring

educators with a bachelor's in a subject other than teaching earn a master's in teaching or undergo alternative teacher certification. Master's in education degrees may help practicing teachers learn new skills and qualify for a raise or promotion reason why more and more teachers are pursuing higher level of education such as doctorate degree.

Sub-problem No. 2: What is the level of teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers themselves in terms of:

3.1 Classroom Management

As shown in Table 10, the assessment of the teachers' competency as to classroom management rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.16. One item rated as Highly Competent which is maintains safe and orderly classroom free from destructions with composite weighted mean of 4.29 as rank 1. Four (4) items rated as Highly Competent, namely: manages classroom structure to engage learners in a meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within the range of physical learning environment; and establishes routines and procedures to maximize instructional time with both composite weighted mean of 4.14 as rank 2 and 3; manages learners' behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline with both composite weighted mean of 4.13 as rank 4; and uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences with composite weighted mean of 4.08 as rank 5.

Table 10
Assessment as to Classroom Management

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Manages classroom structure to engage learners in a meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within the range of physical learning environment.	4.19	C	4.15	C	4.07	C	4.14	C	2.5
2. Manages learners' behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline.	4.30	HC	4.09	C	4.01	C	4.13	C	4
3. Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences.	4.19	C	4.02	C	4.03	C	4.08	C	5
4. Maintains safe and orderly classroom free from destructions.	4.30	HC	4.38	HC	4.18	C	4.29	HC	1
5. Establishes routines and procedures to maximize instructional time.	3.97	C	4.31	HC	4.15	C	4.14	C	2.5

Overall Mean	Weighted Mean	4.19	C	4.19	C	4.09	C	4.16	C
<i>Legend:</i>									
Range	Scale	Verbal Interpretation		Symbol					
5	4.20-5.00	Highly Competent		HC					
4	3.40-4.19	Competent		C					
3	2.60-3.39	Moderately Competent		MC					
2	1.80-2.59	Least Competent		LC					
1	1.00-1.79	Not Competent		NC					

As to groups of respondents' assessments on the teachers' competency as to classroom management rated as Competent, such as: school heads; and master teachers with both overall weighted mean of 4.19; and teachers with overall weighted mean of 4.09.

It can be inferred from the data as to the assessment of the three groups of respondents with regards to classroom management rated as Competent. This could be interpreted that teacher has to be well-oriented in establishing routines that maximize learning experience. Structuring learning and teaching context to achieve meaningful exploration and discovery enhance learners' performance. Likewise, it is also important that teachers are capable of imposing classroom positive discipline without applying violent.

This finding is relevant to the statement of Young (2014) she stated that classroom management is one of the most important factors affecting student learning. Simply put, students learn better when they view the learning environment as positive and supportive. A positive classroom environment is one in which students feel a sense of belongingness, trust others, and feel encourages to tackle challenges, take risk without exposing to any form of violence. Such an environment provides established routines, relevant content, clear learning goals and feedback, opportunities to build social skills, and strategies to help students succeed.

3.2 Mastery of the Subjects

Table 11

Assessment as to Mastery of the Subjects

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Uses appropriate pedagogy to achieve objectives of the lesson.	4.30	HC	3.83	C	4.14	C	4.09	C	5
2. Provides varied learning activities congruent with the objective of the lesson.	4.30	HC	4.05	C	4.11	C	4.15	C	3
3. Encourages interactive participation of the learners.	4.30	HC	4.47	HC	4.15	C	4.31	HC	1
4. Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	4.30	HC	4.09	C	4.01	C	4.13	C	4
5. Uses variety of teaching approaches and techniques appropriate to the learners and the subject matter.	4.30	HC	4.12	C	4.11	C	4.18	C	2
Overall Weighted Mean	4.30	HC	4.11	C	4.10	C	4.17	C	

As revealed in Table 11, the assessment of the teachers' proficiency as to mastery of subjects rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.17. One item rated as Highly Competent which is encourages interactive participation of the learners with composite weighted mean of 4.31 as rank 1. Four (4) items rated as Competent, these are: uses variety of teaching approaches and techniques appropriate to the learners and the subject matter with composite weighted mean of 4.18 as rank 2; provides varied learning activities congruent with the objective of the lesson with composite weighted mean of 4.15 as rank 3; applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills with composite weighted mean of 4.13 as rank 4; and uses appropriate pedagogy to achieve objectives of the lesson with composite weighted mean of 4.09 as rank 5.

As to groups of respondents' assessments on the teachers' competency as to mastery of subjects are as follows: school heads rated as Highly Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.30; master teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.11; and teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.10.

It can be gleaned from the data as to the assessment of the three groups of respondents with regards to mastery of the subjects was rated as Competent. This could be interpreted that teacher utilize strategies and approaches appropriate to the level of students understanding. Likewise, teachers must have the ability to design lessons which are well coordinated based on the content of the subject matter and the curriculum.

This finding is related to the study of Uzzo, Graves, Shay, Harford and Thompson (2018) which stated that mastery of the subject is the ability of the teacher to teach and explain the subject matter well in such a way that students will be easily grasp its content. Teachers with the good knowledge on variety of strategies and technique in teaching is able to plan lesson by

way of highlighting the main points of the lesson with clarity of the knowledge content.

3.3 Instructional Material Development

As exposed in Table 12, the assessment of the teachers' competency as to instructional material development rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.12. One item rated as Highly Competent which is

Table 12

Assessment as to Instructional Material Development

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Develops instructional material aligned with the curriculum and subject area.	4.30	HC	4.22	HC	4.08	C	4.20	HC	1
2. Designs indigenous / local instructional material for development.	4.30	HC	3.80	C	3.89	C	4.00	C	5
3. Provides activities and materials which fits the learners' learning style, goal and culture.	4.30	HC	4.18	C	4.04	C	4.17	C	2
4. Creates instructional materials that reinforce application of concept and skills in real life situation.	4.30	HC	3.99	C	4.02	C	4.10	C	4
5. Constructs materials with varied enrichment	4.30	HC	4.12	C	3.93	C	4.12	C	3

activities to nurture the desire for further learning.									
Overall									
Weighted Mean	4.30	HC	4.06	C	3.99	C	4.12	C	

develops instructional material aligned with the curriculum and subject area with composite weighted mean of 4.20 as rank 1. Four (4) items rated as Competent, namely: provides activities and materials which fit the learners' learning style, goal and culture with composite weighted mean of 4.17 as rank 2; constructs materials with varied enrichment activities to nurture the desire for further learning with composite weighted mean of 4.12 as rank 3; creates instructional materials that reinforce application of concept and skills in real life situation with composite weighted mean of 4.10 as rank 4; and designs indigenous / local instructional material for development with composite weighted mean of 4.00 as rank 5.

As to groups of respondents' assessments on the teachers' competency as to instructional material development are as follows: school heads rated as Highly Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.30; master teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.06; and teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 3.99.

It can be deduced from the data as to the assessment of the three groups of respondents with regards to instructional material development was rated as Competent. This could be interpreted that teacher should develop instructional material aligned with the curriculum and subject area. The content of activities must relevant, appropriate and applicable to the needs of the learners as well as the community.

These findings appear in the study of Zeiger (2010) who described that teacher must be capable of developing instructional materials to meet student needs and cover the standard. This require knowing how to choose and

create materials to accommodate students at different level and employ varied teaching strategies, best practices and other appropriate teaching approaches which allow competent teachers to effectively present the content of the curriculum.

3.4 Teaching Strategies and Approaches

Table 13

Assessment as to Teaching Strategies and Approaches

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Uses appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT to address learning goals.	4.30	HC	4.31	HC	4.10	C	4.24	HC	1
2. Engages in mentoring with colleagues to improve teaching.	4.30	HC	4.09	C	3.88	C	4.09	C	3
3. Provides activities which address a range of learning styles / multiple intelligences.	4.30	HC	4.12	C	3.93	C	4.12	C	2
4. Relates authentic learning experiences in a real-world context.	4.30	HC	3.99	C	3.93	C	4.07	C	4
5. Conducts action research in the classroom or school.	4.30	HC	3.80	C	3.47	C	3.86	C	5

Overall Weighted Mean	4.30	HC	4.06	C	3.86	C	4.07	C
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As established in Table 13, the assessment of the teachers' competency as to teaching strategies and approaches rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.07. One item rated as Highly Competent which is uses appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT to address learning goals with composite weighted mean of 4.24 as rank 1. Four (4) items rated as Highly Competent, such as: provides activities which address a range of learning styles / multiple intelligences with composite weighted mean of 4.12 as rank 2; engages in mentoring with colleagues to improve teaching with composite weighted mean of 4.09 as rank 3; relates authentic learning experiences in a real-world context with composite weighted mean of 4.07 as rank 4; and conducts action research in the classroom or school with composite weighted mean of 3.86 as rank 5.

As to groups of respondents' assessments on the teachers' competency as to teaching strategies and approaches are as follows: school heads rated as Highly Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.30; master teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.06; and teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 3.86.

It can be inferred from the data as to the assessment of the three groups of respondents with regards to teaching strategies and approaches was rated as Competent. This could be interpreted that teacher use appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT to address learning goals and meet the constantly changing needs of learners.

This finding matched to the study of Tripathi (2016) he stated that in modern education, the demand in designing innovative teaching strategies to meet the needs of today's diverse technological learners continue to grow. This contributed to the evolution and development of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education. ICT requires a wide range of

presentation, control and feedback where devices may be employed such as teaching machines, simulators and computers.

3.5 Communication Skills

As identified in Table 14, the assessment of the teachers' competency as to communication skills rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.20. Four (4) items rated as Highly Competent, these are: uses words appropriate for the pupils' level of understanding with composite weighted mean of 4.22 as rank 1; presents ideas clearly, logically and comprehensively; with both composite weighted mean of 4.21 as rank 2;

Table 14

Assessment as to Communication Skills

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Shows proficiency in the required language of instruction.	4.30	HC	4.25	HC	4.01	C	4.19	C	5
2. Explains learning goals, concepts and processes clearly and accurately to the learners.	4.30	HC	4.25	HC	4.05	C	4.20	HC	3.5
3. Uses words appropriate for the pupils' level of understanding.	4.30	HC	4.28	HC	4.08	C	4.22	HC	1
4. Presents ideas clearly, logically and comprehensively.	4.30	HC	4.25	HC	4.07	C	4.21	HC	2
5. Uses expression to motivate and enhance learners' self-confidence.	4.30	HC	4.25	HC	4.06	C	4.20	HC	3.5
Overall Weighted Mean	4.30	HC	4.26	HC	4.05	C	4.20	HC	

and explains learning goals, concepts and processes clearly and accurately to the learners; and uses expression to motivate and enhance learners' self-confidence with both composite weighted mean of 4.20 as rank 3 and 4. One item rated as Competent which is shows competency in the required language of instruction with composite weighted mean of 4.19 as rank 5.

As to groups of respondents' assessments on the teachers' competency as to communication skills are as follows: school heads rated as Highly Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.30; master teachers rated as Highly Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.26; and teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.05.

It can be concluded from the data as to the assessment of the three groups of respondents with regards to communication skills was rated as Competent. This could be interpreted that teacher use words appropriate to the learners' level of understanding. Likewise, the language use in teaching must presents ideas clearly, logically and comprehensively.

This finding is parallel to the research conducted by Young and Travis (2018). They believed on the importance of communication skills in teaching for it represent your thought process, academic background, social skills, and cultural views. Accordingly, effective communication through the use of a chosen language implies good or pleasant speech and this turn requires not only a clear, well-modulated voice but also speech that is easily understood and is accurate in the production of the individual sounds and in the selection of words. Good skills and solid choices in the use of language can help learners better understand the knowledge being imparted.

3.6 Learning Assessment and Reporting

Table 15

Assessment as to Learning Assessment and Reporting

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Constructs valid and reliable formative and summative test.	4.30	HC	4.09	C	4.16	C	4.18	C	2
2. Uses appropriate non-traditional assessment techniques and tools (e.g. portfolio, journals, and rubrics).	4.30	HC	3.99	C	3.87	C	4.05	C	5
3. Interprets and uses test results to improve teaching and learning.	4.30	HC	4.12	C	4.02	C	4.15	C	3
4. Keeps accurate records of grades performance levels of learners.	4.30	HC	4.35	HC	4.17	C	4.27	HC	1
5. Provides timely accurate feedback to learners to encourage them to reflect on and monitor their own	4.30	HC	4.02	C	4.06	C	4.13	C	4

learning growth.									
Overall									
Weighted Mean	4.30	HC	4.11	C	4.06	C	4.16	C	

As presented in Table 15, the assessment of the teachers' competency as to learning assessment and reporting rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.16. One item rated as Highly Competent which is keeps accurate records of grades performance levels of learners with composite weighted mean of 4.27 as rank 1. Four (4) items rated as Highly Competent, namely: constructs valid and reliable formative and summative test with composite weighted mean of 4.18 as rank 2; interprets and uses test results to improve teaching and learning with composite weighted mean of 4.15 as rank 3; provides timely accurate feedback to learners to encourage them to reflect on and monitor their own learning growth with composite weighted mean of 4.13 as rank 4; and uses appropriate non-traditional assessment techniques and tools (e.g. portfolio, journals, and rubrics) with composite weighted mean of 4.05 as rank 5.

As to groups of respondents' assessments on the teachers' competency as to learning assessment and reporting are as follows: school heads rated as Highly Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.30; master teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.11; and teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.06.

It can be determined from the data as to the assessment of the three groups of respondents with regards to learning assessment and reporting was rated as Competent. This could be interpreted that teacher keep accurate records of grades performance levels of learners. Information gathered from the recorded data may be used as tool in identifying the strengths and weaknesses of learners for more effective teaching process.

This finding is relevant to the study of Klenowski and Smith (2014) that in order for teachers to be effective, they must have a repertoire of skills and

understanding to design quality assessment and to use achievement standard and evidence as a means to discern, monitor and improve learning as well as judge the qualities of student work. Assessment and reporting must be a shared enterprise, with benefits accruing to all students, including those who are marginalized and disengaged and those who are identified as gifted and talented.

3.7 Community Linkages

As reflected in Table 16, the assessment of the teachers' competency as to community linkages rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.13. Two (2) items rated as Highly Competent, such as: informs learners, parents and other stakeholders regarding school policies and procedures with composite weighted mean of 4.24 as rank 1; and recognizes the various activities, programs

Table 16
Assessment as to Community Linkages

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Identifies various community resources available to enhance learning.	4.30	HC	3.93	C	3.83	C	4.02	C	5
2. Involves parents / community in sharing accountability.	4.30	HC	4.05	C	3.94	C	4.10	C	3
3. Knows realities outside the classroom to make learning relevant.	4.30	HC	4.02	C	3.93	C	4.08	C	4
4. Informs learners, parents and	4.30	HC	4.28	HC	4.13	C	4.24	HC	1

other stakeholders regarding school policies and procedures.									
5. Recognizes the various activities, programs and projects where school–community partnerships are involved.	4.30	HC	4.28	HC	4.05	C	4.21	HC	2
Overall Weighted Mean	4.30	HC	4.11	C	3.98	C	4.13	C	

and projects where school–community partnerships are involved with composite weighted mean of 4.21 as rank 2. Three (3) items rated as Competent, these are: involves parents / community in sharing accountability with composite weighted mean of 4.10 as rank 3; knows realities outside the classroom to make learning relevant with composite weighted mean of 4.08 as rank 4; and identifies various community resources available to enhance learning with composite weighted mean of 4.02 as rank 5.

As to groups of respondents' assessments on the teachers' competency as to community linkages are as follows: school heads rated as Highly Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.30; master teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 4.11; and teachers rated as Competent with overall weighted mean of 3.98.

It can be determined from the data as to the assessment of the three groups of respondents with regards to community linkages was rated as Competent. This could be interpreted those parents and other stakeholder are well-informed regarding school policies and procedures which may help promote good relationship among teachers and other stakeholders. Likewise, recognizing

various activities, programs and projects of school by the community contributes to the success of the schools' mission and vision.

This finding is connected to the study of Epstein (2019) that building community linkages is now part of an effective teaching, Community involvement must focus on engaging all families in ways that improve the school climate and promote academic and behavioral results for students. Goal-linked family and community engagement activities help improve student attendance, achievement, behavior, and other indicators of success in school.

Table 17

Summary of the Teachers' Competencies

Indicator	School Heads		Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Classroom Management	4.19	C	4.19	C	4.09	C	4.16	C	3.5
2. Mastery of the Subjects	4.30	HC	4.11	C	4.10	C	4.17	C	2
3. Instructional Material Development	4.30	HC	4.06	C	3.99	C	4.12	C	6
4. Teaching Strategies and Approaches	4.30	HC	4.06	C	3.86	C	4.07	C	7
5. Communication Skills	4.30	HC	4.26	HC	4.05	C	4.20	HC	1
6. Learning Assessment and Reporting	4.30	HC	4.11	C	4.06	C	4.16	C	3.5
7. Community Linkages	4.30	HC	4.11	C	3.98	C	4.13	C	5
Grand Mean	4.28	HC	4.13	C	4.02	C	4.14	C	

Table 17 summarizes the assessment on the teachers' competency rated as Competent with the grand mean of 4.14. One item rated as Highly Competent which is communication skills with composite weighted mean of 4.20 as rank 1. Six (6) items rated as Competent, namely: mastery of the subjects with composite weighted mean of 4.17 as rank 2; classroom management; and learning assessment and reporting with both composite weighted mean of 4.16 as rank 3 and 4; community linkages with composite weighted mean of 4.13 as rank 5; instructional material development with composite weighted mean of 4.12 as

rank 6; and teaching strategies and approaches with composite weighted mean of 4.07 as rank 7.

Generally, the groups of respondents' assessments on the teachers' competency are as follows: school heads rated as Highly Competent with the grand mean of 4.28; master teachers rated as Competent with the grand mean of 4.13; and teachers rated as Competent with the grand mean of 4.02.

This implied that the teachers are still in need of improving their teaching competency from classroom management to community link aspect of education in order to be acquainted with the current trend and issues in developing the lifelong education of the learners in response to the 21st century skills needed toward global competitiveness.

This finding is associated to the statement of Salandanan (2012) that the quality of education depends primarily upon the quality of teachers. The proficiency of teacher in terms of knowledge of the subject matter and skills in teaching methodologies spell success in the teaching profession. A teacher should be able to feed the minds of the learners with an advance and deeper understanding of the lesson accurately and confidently.

Sub-problem No. 3: Is there any significant difference in the assessment of the respondents of the abovementioned variables?

Table 18

Comparative Assessment of Teachers' Competency

Areas of Concern		SS	MS	F-value	Interpretation	Decision
1. Classroom Management	Bet. Grp	0.173	0.086	1.7327	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Within Grp.	0.600	0.050	7		
2. Mastery of the Subjects	Bet. Grp.	0.615	0.307	6.1465	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Grp.	0.600	0.500	6		

3. Instructional Material Development	Bet. Grp. Within Grp.	1.303 0.600	0.651 0.050	13.026 5	Significant	Reject Ho
4. Teaching Strategies and Approaches	Bet. Grp. Within Grp.	2.404 0.600	1.202 0.050	24.003 5	Significant	Reject Ho
5. Communication Skills	Bet. Grp. Within Grp.	0.860 0.600	0.430 0.50	8.6045 4	Significant	Reject Ho
6. Learning Assessment and Reporting	Bet. Grp. Within Grp.	0.812 0.600	0.406 0.050	8.1201 3	Significant	Reject Ho
7. Community Linkages	Bet. Grp. Within Grp.	1.323 0.600	0.661 0.050	13.226 3	Significant	Reject Ho

Legend: df of 137 @ Level of Significance: 0.05 with critical value of 3.00

As manifested in Table 18, the computed F-values are as follows: mastery of subject (6.14656); instructional materials development (13.0265); teaching strategies and approaches (24.0035); communication skills (8.60454); learning assessment and reporting (8.12013); and community linkages (13.2263) were all higher than the critical value of 3.00 with 2 and 137 degree of freedom with 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there are significant differences on the teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

On the other hand, the computed F-value in classroom management which is 1.73277 which is lower than the critical values of 3.00 with 2 and 137 with the degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance with 2 and 137. Hence, there is no significant difference on the teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

This implied that the assessment of the respondents of the teachers' competency has similar view and perception that the teachers should possess several characteristics and skills that help to improve the overall performance of the school in terms of delivery quality instruction.

This finding supports the study of Bilbao (2015) who identified teacher as an extraordinary person in whose hands lie the future of the country. Thus, a teacher must become globally competent who possesses qualities, skills, knowledge, views, with wider breadth and deeper sense so they could cater the 21st century learners more effectively.

Sub-problem No. 4: Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' competency and professional profile?

As revealed in Table 19, the computed t-values are: classroom management (64.36); mastery of the subjects (54.62); instructional material development (94.76); teaching strategies and approaches (47.88); communication skills (54.51); learning assessment and reporting (46.65); and community linkages (64.72) were all higher than the critical values of 1.943 at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 16. Hence, there is significant relationship between the teachers' competency and professional profile. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Table 19

Relationship Between the Teachers' Competency and Professional Profile

Indicator	r-value	VI	Critical value	df	t-value	Int.	Decision
1. Classroom Management	0.89	VS C	1.943	1 6	64.3 6	Significant	Reject H ₀
2. Mastery of the Subjects	0.96	VS C	1.943	1 6	54.6 2	Significant	Reject H ₀
3. Instructional Material	0.96	VS C	1.943	1 6	94.7 6	Significant	Reject H ₀

4.	Development Teaching Strategies and Approaches	0.97	VS C	1.943	1 6	47.8 8	Significa nt	Reject H _o
5.	Communication Skills	0.95	VS C	1.943	1 6	54.5 1	Significa nt	Reject H _o
6.	Learning Assessment and Reporting	0.96	VS C	1.943	1 6	46.6 5	Significa nt	Reject H _o
7.	Community Linkages	0.96	VS C	1.943	1 6	64.7 2	Significa nt	Reject H _o

Legend: level of significance @0.05

0.80 – 0.99 Very Strong Correlation (VSC)

0.60 – 0.79 Strong Correlation (SC)

0.40 – 0.59 Moderate Correlation (MC)

0.20 – 0.39 Weak Correlation (WC)

0.01 – 0.19 Negligible Correlation

This finding is contrary to the study of Pulgo (2017) on the relationship of teachers' competencies and performance it was shown that there was no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the extent of importance of teachers' competencies. This entailed those qualifications plays a minor role in assessing whether the teacher is highly competent.

Sub-problem No. 5: What is the performance of the learners in English based on Phil-IRI result?

As revealed in Table 20, the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory result, the level of reading comprehension, are as follows: for the Academic Year 2016-2017, frustration have 1165 or 18.87 percent; instructional have 1392 or 22.55 percent; independent have 1878 or 30.42 percent; and non-reader have 1738 or 28.15 percent with a verbal interpretation of good. For

Table 20

Performance of the Learners in English

Academic Year	Frustration		Instructional		Independent		Non-reader		Total		Verbal Interpretation
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
2016-2017	116	18.	139	22.	187	30.	173	28.1	64	10	G
2017-2018	152	31.	101	20.	603	12.	174	35.7	48	10	A
2018-2019	111	27.	882	21.	539	13.	157	38.3	41	10	A
2019	8	16		43		10	7	1	16	0	

Legend:

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	90-100	Excellent	E
4	80-89	Very Good	VG
3	70-79	Good	G
2	50-69	Average	A
1	49-below	Poor	P

the Academic Year 2017-2018, frustration have 1520 or 31.18 percent; instructional have 1010 or 20.72 percent; independent have 603 or 12.37 percent; and non-reader have 1742 or 35.73 percent with a verbal interpretation of average. For the Academic Year 2018-2019, frustration have 1118 or 27.16 percent; instructional have 882 or 21.43 percent; independent have 539 or 13.10 percent; and non-reader have 1577 or 38.31 percent with a verbal interpretation of average.

This implied that there is a need to prepare intervention program for teachers to enhance their competency which may result to a better and improve performance of the learners in English.

Sub-problem No. 6: Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' competency and learners' performance?

Table 21**Comparison Between Teachers' Proficiency and Learners' Performance – Frustration Reader**

Indicator	r-value	VI	Critical value	df	t-value	Int.	Decision
1. Classroom Management	0.96	VSC	1.943	6	9.81	Significant	Reject H _o
2. Mastery of the Subjects	0.95	VSC	1.943	6	8.91	Significant	Reject H _o
3. Instructional Material Development	0.95	VSC	1.943	6	8.59	Significant	Reject H _o
4. Teaching Strategies and Approaches	0.94	VSC	1.943	6	8.39	Significant	Reject H _o
5. Communication Skills	0.95	VSC	1.943	6	9.41	Significant	Reject H _o
6. Learning Assessment and Reporting	0.95	VSC	1.943	6	8.86	Significant	Reject H _o
7. Community Linkages	0.95	VSC	1.943	6	8.75	Significant	Reject H _o

Legend: level of significance @0.05

0.80 – 0.99 Very Strong Correlation (VSC)

0.60 – 0.79 Strong Correlation (SC)

0.40 – 0.59 Moderate Correlation (MC)

0.20 – 0.39 Weak Correlation (WC)

0.01 – 0.19 Negligible Correlation (NC)

As revealed in Table 21, the computed t-values are: classroom management (9.81); mastery of the subjects (8.91); instructional material development (8.59); teaching strategies and approaches (8.39); communication skills (9.41); learning assessment and reporting (8.86); and community linkages (8.75) were all higher than the critical values of 1.943 at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 6. Hence, there is significant relationship between the teachers' proficiency and learner's performance – frustration readers. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

As revealed in Table 22, the computed t-values are: classroom management (56.61); mastery of the subjects (113.36); instructional material

development (98.13); teaching strategies and approaches (58.45); communication skills (53.42); learning assessment and reporting (100.26); and community linkages (75.57) were all higher than the critical values of 1.943 at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 6. Hence, there is significant relationship between the teachers' proficiency and learner's performance – instructional readers. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Table 22

Comparison Between Teachers' Proficiency and Learners' Performance – Instructional Reader

Indicator	r-value	VI	Critical value	df	t-value	Int.	Decision
1. Classroom Management	0.99	VSC	1.943	6	56.61	Significant	Reject H ₀
2. Mastery of the Subjects	0.99	VSC	1.943	6	113.36	Significant	Reject H ₀
3. Instructional Material Development	0.99	VSC	1.943	6	98.13	Significant	Reject H ₀
4. Teaching Strategies and Approaches	0.99	VSC	1.943	6	58.45	Significant	Reject H ₀
5. Communication Skills	0.99	VSC	1.943	6	53.42	Significant	Reject H ₀
6. Learning Assessment and Reporting	0.99	VSC	1.943	6	100.26	Significant	Reject H ₀
7. Community Linkages	0.99	VSC	1.943	6	75.57	Significant	Reject H ₀

Legend: level of significance @0.05

0.80 – 0.99 Very Strong Correlation (VSC)

0.60 – 0.79 Strong Correlation (SC)

0.40 – 0.59 Moderate Correlation (MC)

0.20 – 0.39 Weak Correlation (WC)

0.01 – 0.19 Negligible Correlation (NC)

As revealed in Table 23, the computed t-values are: classroom management (4.36); mastery of the subjects (4.62); instructional material development (4.76); teaching strategies and approaches (4.88); communication skills (4.51); learning assessment and reporting (4.65); and community linkages (4.72) were all higher than the critical values of 1.943 at

0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 6. Hence, there is significant relationship between the teachers' proficiency and learner's performance – independent readers. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Table 23

Comparison Between Teachers' Proficiency and Learners' Performance – Independent Readers

Indicator	r-value	VI	Critical value	df	t-value	Int.	Decision
1. Classroom Management	0.84	VSC	1.943	6	4.36	Significant	Reject H _o
2. Mastery of the Subjects	0.86	VSC	1.943	6	4.62	Significant	Reject H _o
3. Instructional Material Development	0.86	VSC	1.943	6	4.76	Significant	Reject H _o
4. Teaching Strategies and Approaches	0.87	VSC	1.943	6	4.88	Significant	Reject H _o
5. Communication Skills	0.85	VSC	1.943	6	4.51	Significant	Reject H _o
6. Learning Assessment and Reporting	0.86	VSC	1.943	6	4.65	Significant	Reject H _o
7. Community Linkages	0.86	VSC	1.943	6	4.72	Significant	Reject H _o

Legend: level of significance @0.05

0.80 – 0.99 Very Strong Correlation (VSC)

0.60 – 0.79 Strong Correlation (SC)

0.40 – 0.59 Moderate Correlation (MC)

0.20 – 0.39 Weak Correlation (WC)

0.01 – 0.19 Negligible Correlation (NC)

As revealed in Table 24, the computed t-values are: classroom management (14.74); mastery of the subjects (13.42); instructional material development (12.41); teaching strategies and approaches (11.55); communication skills (13.35);

Table 24**Comparison Between Teachers' Proficiency and Learners' Performance – Non-Readers**

Indicator	r-value	VI	Critical value	df	t-value	Int.	Decision
1. Classroom Management	0.98	VSC	1.943	6	14.74	Significant	Reject H ₀
2. Mastery of the Subjects	0.97	VSC	1.943	6	13.42	Significant	Reject H ₀
3. Instructional Material Development	0.97	VSC	1.943	6	12.41	Significant	Reject H ₀
4. Teaching Strategies and Approaches	0.97	VSC	1.943	6	11.55	Significant	Reject H ₀
5. Communication Skills	0.97	VSC	1.943	6	13.35	Significant	Reject H ₀
6. Learning Assessment and Reporting	0.97	VSC	1.943	6	13.04	Significant	Reject H ₀
7. Community Linkages	0.97	VSC	1.943	6	12.47	Significant	Reject H ₀

Legend: level of significance @0.050.80 – 0.99 *Very Strong Correlation (VSC)*0.60 – 0.79 *Strong Correlation (SC)*0.40 – 0.59 *Moderate Correlation (MC)*0.20 – 0.39 *Weak Correlation (WC)*0.01 – 0.19 *Negligible Correlation (NC)*

learning assessment and reporting (13.04); and community linkages (12.47) were all higher than the critical values of 1.943 at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 6. Hence, there is significant relationship between the teachers' proficiency and learner's performance – non-readers. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

This finding is relative to the study of Teygong, Moses & Daniel (2017) also believed that teachers have important influence on learner' academic achievement. Their study found out that teachers utilized question and answer method, problem solving and demonstration as main method of teaching. The findings meant that teacher who used various teaching method and exceptional teaching competence were able to post positive result in their

classes than those who relied on one method of teaching. Due to this, a cross-sectional study of questionnaire survey research design was conducted in this respect. Data on teaching qualification, characteristics and competence were generated from the target respondents. The questionnaires were distributed through email and, drop-off and pick procedures. Overall, findings from the testing of hypothesis indicate that there is a significant relationship between teachers' qualification and students' performance.

Sub-problem No. 7 What are the problems encountered by the respondents?

Table 25

Problems Encountered on the Teachers' Competency

Indicator	School Principals		Master Teachers		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
1. Poor attendance and study habits of learners.	1.81	LE	3.57	E	3.62	E	3.00	ME	1.5
2. Lack of skills and trainings.	1.81	LE	3.12	ME	3.03	ME	2.65	ME	3
3. Lack of support from higher school officials.	1.14	NE	2.38	LE	2.90	ME	2.14	LE	9
4. Lack of knowledge on the use of ICT.	1.37	NE	2.44	LE	2.55	LE	2.12	LE	10
5. Lack of parents / community cooperation and support.	1.70	NE	2.64	ME	3.09	ME	2.48	LE	4
6. Lack of textbooks and other instructional supplies.	1.14	NE	2.76	ME	3.17	ME	2.36	LE	7

7. Lack of facilities for conducive teaching and learning process.	1.81	LE	2.28	LE	2.75	ME	2.28	LE	8
8. Lack of sufficient time in teaching.	2.14	LE	2.47	LE	2.65	ME	2.42	LE	5.5
9. Lack of learners' proper nutrition resulting to poor focus.	1.14	NE	2.93	ME	3.19	ME	2.42	LE	5.5
10. Lack of learners' study habits.	1.81	LE	3.57	E	3.63	E	3.00	ME	1.5
Overall Weighted Mean	1.59	NE	2.82	ME	3.06	ME	2.49	LE	

Legend:

Range	Scale	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.20-5.00	Highly Encountered	HE
4	3.40-4.19	Encountered	E
3	2.60-3.39	Moderately Encountered	ME
2	1.80-2.59	Least Encountered	LE
1	1.00-1.79	Not Encountered	NE

As manifested in Table 25, the assessment of the problems encountered on the teachers' proficiency rated as Least Encountered with overall weighted mean of 2.49. Three (3) items rated as Moderately Encountered, such as: poor attendance and study habits of learners; and lack of learners' study habits with both composite weighted mean of 3.00 as rank 1 and 2; and lack of skills and trainings with composite weighted mean of 2.65 as rank 3. Seven (7) items rated as Least Encountered, these are: lack of parents / community cooperation and support with composite weighted mean of 2.48 as rank 4; lack of sufficient time in teaching; and Lack of learners' proper nutrition resulting to poor focus with both composite weighted mean of 2.42 as rank 5 and 6; lack of textbooks and other instructional supplies with composite weighted mean of 2.36 as rank 7; lack of facilities for conducive teaching and

learning process with composite weighted mean of 2.28 as rank 8; lack of support from higher school officials with composite weighted mean of 2.14 as rank 9; and lack of knowledge on the use of ICT with composite weighted mean of 2.12 as rank 10.

As to groups of respondents' assessments on the problems encountered on the teachers' proficiency are as follows: teachers rated as Moderately Encountered with overall weighted mean of 3.06; master teachers rated as Moderately Encountered with overall weighted mean of 2.82; and school heads rated as Not Encountered with overall weighted mean of 1.59.

This finding is relative to the study of Wolf (2014) described the characteristics of competent teachers' knowledge. Competent teachers' perceptions of student learning difficulties: feel accountable for problems with the student learning (for what they do/don't learn); believe they are capable of finding solutions to student learning problem; learning problems were related to lesson structure and organization. Conceptions of knowledge; showed willingness to learn; tried to identify important components and create steps when teaching new concepts; and relied on logical or technical explanations to justify lesson content. Reflective Practice: recognized a range of student ability and knowledge; lessons were linked to continual student assessment (informal, subjective, and reflexive) and used appraisals to identify difficulties and find supporting activities; and made decisions for teaching activities based on subjective student performance observations.

Sub-problem No 8. Based on the findings, what intervention scheme may be offered for implementation?

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher proposed an intervention scheme which aim to enhance the competency level of grade two teacher in teaching English. It focused on the domains such as of classroom management, mastery of the subjects, instructional material

development, teaching strategies and approaches, communication skills, learning assessment and reporting and community linkages.

A. Rationale

This intervention scheme for grade two teachers is based from the result of the study which were identified and pinpoint by their weaknesses as basis for the preparation of the training matrix according to the expected task that will enhance the skills of teachers to ensure efficient, effective and excellent performance to achieve the goal and objective of the academic program.

B. Objectives

1. Provide a template for teachers' intervention scheme;
 2. Enumerate the priority competencies for the intervention scheme;
- and
3. Give detailed activities that address the priority competencies the grade 2 English teachers need for improvement.

c. MATRIX OF AN INTERVENTION SCHEME FOR GRADE 2 ENGLISH TEACHERS

Key Area Result	Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Person Involved	Time Frame	Source of Fund	Performance Indicator
Teaching Strategies and Approaches	Conducts action research in the classroom or school.	Carry on training and workshop on how to write action research.	Research Coordinator, Master Teacher, Teacher	June -May	GAA	100% of teachers submit an action research
	Relates authentic learning experiences in a real-world context.	Design lesson plans that will engage students in real-world context.	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June -May	GAA	100% of teachers produce lesson plan with real-world context.

	Engages in mentoring with colleagues to improve teaching.	Conduct mentoring and coaching to enhance teaching	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - August	GAA	100% of teachers were given technical assistance and mentoring
Instructional Material Development	Designs indigenous / local instructional material for development.	Engage teacher in instructional material development	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100% of teachers developed localized and indigenized learning materials
	Creates instructional materials that reinforce application of concept and skills in real life situation.	Conduct training and workshop on how to design instructional materials based in real life situation.	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100% of teachers were able to design instructional materials based in real life situation.
	Constructs materials with varied enrichment activities to nurture the desire for further learning.	Develop instructional material for enrichment and follow-ups	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100% of teachers had a well-prepared lesson plan with enrichment activities
	Identifies various community resources available to enhance learning.	Conduct survey and evaluation to identify available community resources.	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher, Parent	April - May	GAA	100% of parents and stakeholders answer the survey

Community Linkages						and evaluation
	Knows realities outside the classroom to make learning relevant.	Coordinate with the stakeholders outside the classroom.	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher, Parent	April -May	GAA	100% of parents and stakeholders are cooperative and supportive
	Involves parents / community in sharing accountability.	Encourage shared accountability among stakeholders.	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher, Parent	June - March	GAA	100% of parents shared accountability
Learning Assessment and Reporting	Uses appropriate non-traditional assessment techniques and tools (e.g. portfolio, journals, and rubrics).	Conduct training and workshop in portfolio making.	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100% of learners submit portfolio.
	Provides timely accurate feedback to learners to encourage them to reflect on and monitor their own learning growth.	Design assessment tool for accurate feedback and monitoring.	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100% of teachers use acceptable assessment tool
	Interprets and uses test results to improve	Evaluate test results to improve	School Head, Master	June - March	GAA	100% acceptability of the

	teaching and learning.	teaching and learning	Teacher, Teacher			assessment tool
Classroom Management	Uses differentiated developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences.	Conduct orientation and seminars on gender and development program	Guidance Teacher School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100% of Teachers participate in the orientation and seminar.
	Manages learners' behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline.	Design classroom conducive to teaching	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA / SEF	100% of classroom were conducive to teaching-learning process
	Establishes routines and procedures to maximize instructional time.	Monitor schedule to maximize teaching	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - August	GAA	100% of routines were established
	Uses appropriate pedagogy to achieve objectives of the lesson.	Develop lesson plan align to the curriculum content.	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100% of teachers develop lesson plan align to the curriculum content.

Mastery of the Subjects	Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	Conduct seminars and trainings to enhance teaching	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100% of teachers applied innovative teaching approaches and techniques
	Provides varied learning activities congruent with the objective of the lesson	Develop activities align to the curriculum content	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100% of activities were align to the curriculum content
Communication Skills	Shows proficiency in the required language of instruction.	Conduct trainings and workshops to develop communication skill in teaching	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100% of teachers used appropriate language in teaching
	Explains learning goals, concepts and processes clearly and accurately to the learners.	Use language according to learners' level of understanding	School Head, Master Teacher, Teacher	June - March	GAA	100 of teachers presented accurate learning goals.
	Uses expression to motivate and	Apply language according to learners'	School Head, Master	June - March	GAA	100 of teachers presented accurate

	enhance learners' self-confidence	level of understanding	Teacher, Teacher			learning goals.
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CHAPTER 5

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendation

Summary

The following are the findings of the specific problems drawn from the study:

1. On the professional profile of the teachers handling Grade 2 learners. The overall qualifications of the respondents are 30 or 21.43 percent PBET passer; and 110 or 78.57 percent LET passer. For Trainings there are 29 or 20.71 percent who attended international level; 49 or 35.00 percent national level; 11 or 7.86 percent regional level; 41 or 29.29 percent division level; 10 or 7.14 percent district level and there is none for school level. For years in service, 66 or 47.14 percent respondents are more than 10 years in service; 42 or 30.00 percent are 6-10 years; 26 or 18.57 percent are 1-5 years; 6 or 4.29 percent are less than 1 year in service. For educational attainment, 65 or 46.43 percent have bachelor's degree; 60 or 42.86 percent are masters with units; 9 or 6.43 percent have master's degree; and 3 or 2.14 percent are both doctorate with units; and doctorate degree.

2. On the level of teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers themselves. The overall assessment on the training needs of teachers are as follows: communication skills rated as Highly Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.20 as rank 1; mastery of the subjects rated as Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.17 as rank 2; classroom management; and learning assessment and reporting with both rated as Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.16 as rank 3 and 4; community linkages rated as Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.13 as rank 5; instructional material development rated as Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.12 as rank 6; and teaching strategies and approaches rated as Competent with composite weighted mean of 4.07 as rank 7.

3. On a significant difference in the assessment of the respondents of the abovementioned variables. As manifested, the computed F-values are as follows: mastery of subject (6.14656); instructional materials development (13.0265); teaching strategies and approaches (24.0035); communication skills (8.60454); learning assessment and reporting (8.12013); and community linkages (13.2263) were all higher than the critical value of 3.00 with 2 and 137 degree of freedom with 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there are significant differences on the teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, the computed F-value in classroom management which is 1.73277 which is lower than the critical values of 3.00 with 2 and 137 with the degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance with 2 and 137. Hence, there is no significant difference on the teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

4. On a significant relationship between the teachers' competency and professional profile? As revealed in the computed t-values are: classroom management (64.36); mastery of the subjects (54.62); instructional material development (94.76); teaching strategies and approaches (47.88); communication skills (54.51); learning assessment and reporting (46.65); and community linkages (64.72) were all higher than the critical values of 1.943 at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 16. Hence, there is significant relationship between the teachers' competency and professional profile. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

5. On the performance of the learners in English based on Phil-IRI result? As reflected from the documentary analysis, on the learner's performance based on the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory result, the level of reading comprehension, are as follows: for the Academic Year 2016-

2017, frustration have 1165 or 18.87 percent; instructional have 1392 or 22.55 percent; independent have 1878 or 30.42 percent; and non-reader have 1738 or 28.15 percent with a verbal interpretation of good. For the Academic Year 2017-2018, frustration have 1520 or 31.18 percent; instructional have 1010 or 20.72 percent; independent have 603 or 12.37 percent; and non-reader have 1742 or 35.73 percent with a verbal interpretation of average. For the Academic Year 2018-2019, frustration have 1118 or 27.16 percent; instructional have 882 or 21.43 percent; independent have 539 or 13.10 percent; and non-reader have 1577 or 38.31 percent with a verbal interpretation of average.

6. On a significant relationship between the teachers' competency and learners' performance. As revealed in Table 24, the computed t-values are: classroom management (14.74); mastery of the subjects (13.42); instructional material development (12.41); teaching strategies and approaches (11.55); communication skills (13.35); learning assessment and reporting (13.04); and community linkages (12.47) were all higher than the critical values of 1.943 at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 6. Hence, there is significant relationship between the teachers' proficiency and learner's performance – non-readers. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

7. On problems encountered by the respondents. The assessment of the problems encountered on the teachers' competency rated as Least Encountered with overall weighted mean of 2.49. It has been identified as the top ranked among the problems encountered such as poor attendance and study habits of learners; lack of teachers' skills; lack of parents / community cooperation; lack of sufficient time in teaching; lack of learners' proper nutrition resulting to poor focus; lack of textbooks and other instructional supplies; lack of facilities for conducive teaching and learning process; lack

of support from higher school officials; and lack of knowledge on the use of ICT.

8. On the findings of the study. The proposed intervention scheme of teachers has been designed and developed to continuously enhance and much more competent of teachers in teaching English subject.

Conclusions

In the lights of the foregoing finding of the study, the following conclusion are drawn:

1. The professional profile of the teachers handling Grade 2 learners are licensed, well-trained, competent teachers and qualified and equipped with a basic knowledge and skills to teach the learners.
2. The competency of teachers in teaching English for grade 2 learners assessed by the respondents is Competent.
3. There is no significant difference on the teachers' competency as assessed by school heads, master teachers and teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.
4. There is a direct relationship between the teachers' competency and professional profile. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.
5. The performance of the learners in English based on Phil-IRI result for the Academic Year 2016-2017 is Good, for the Academic Year 2017-2018 is Average and for the Academic Year 2018-2019 is Average.
6. There is a direct relationship between the teachers' proficiency and learner's performance in Phil-IRI. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.
7. The problems encountered relative to teachers' proficiency in teaching English rated as Least Encountered.

8. The proposed intervention scheme of teachers has been designed and developed to continuously enhance competent of teachers in teaching English subject.

Recommendation

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented for consideration.

1. The school administrators must ensure that there is a sustainable and continuous development of instructional competence of teachers.

2. The teacher must undergo intensive service training and seminar workshop in teaching methodologies and strategies to expedite the transfer of knowledge and skills to the learners.

3. Sustained the evaluation skills to get the accurate feedbacks on the academic performance of the learners.

4. The problems encountered must be addressed immediately and promptly and taking action needed to enhance the teaching competency of the teachers.

5. Adopt intervention scheme to provide based line of information for policy formulation to access and correct the weaknesses of the teachers concern.

6. Conduct parallel study to discover other variables or areas which are not cover with the framework of the present study.

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Republic of the Philippines
EULOGIO "AMANG" RODRIGUEZ
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
Nagtahan Street, Sampaloc, Manila

GRADUATE SCHOOL

March 6, 2019

DR. JENILYN ROSE B. CORPUZ, CESO VI
Schools Division Superintendent
Division of City Schools
Manila

Madam:

The undersigned is currently undertaking a research study entitled, "**TEACHERS' PROFICIENCY AND LEARNERS' PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 2: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION SCHEME**", in partial requirements for the degree in Masters of Art in Education, major in Administration and Supervision at Eulogio "Amang" Rodriguez Institute of Science and Technology.

In this regard, the undersigned would like to ask permission from your good office to be allowed to administer the survey questionnaire to the prospective respondents in the public elementary schools in Manila

Rest assured that any information gathered will be treated with outmost confidentiality.

Thank you very much and God Bless.

Respectfully yours,

RS
MS. ROSE ANN S. TOSTON
Researcher

Noted by:

EAC
DR. ELEDDIO T. ACTIBAR
Researcher's Adviser

DIST V. Flm

Republic of the Philippines
EULOGIO "AMANG" RODRIGUEZ
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY
Nagtahan Street, Sampaloc, Manila

GRADUATE SCHOOL

Dear Respondents,

Good day!

The undersigned is in the process of gathering data in preparation for this thesis entitled, **"TEACHERS' COMPETENCY AND LEARNERS' PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 2 PUPILS: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION SCHEME"**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree in Masters of Art in Education, major in Administration and Supervision.

To the best of your knowledge, kindly answer the attached questionnaires. Rest assured that any information given will be treated with outmost confidentiality.

Thank you very much.

Truly yours,

MS. ROSE ANN S. TOSTON

Researcher

Appendix B
SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE on the
TEACHERS' COMPETENCY AND LEARNERS' PERFORMANCE OF
GRADE 2 PUPILS: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION SCHEME

Part I: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Name: (optional) _____

School: _____

Directions: Please answer with the complete information asked for the item provided below. Check your choice which you think the most fit to your description.

Type of Respondents:

School Head Master Teacher Teacher

Gender:

Male
 Female

Age Level:

<input type="checkbox"/> 51 years and above	<input type="checkbox"/> 31 - 35 years
<input type="checkbox"/> 46 - 50 years	<input type="checkbox"/> 26 – 30 years
<input type="checkbox"/> 41 - 45 years	<input type="checkbox"/> 25 years and below
<input type="checkbox"/> 36 – 40 years	

Civil Status:

Single Widow/er
 Married Legally Separated

Educational Attainment:

<input type="checkbox"/> Doctorate Degree	<input type="checkbox"/> With MA units
<input type="checkbox"/> With Ph.d/Ed.D units	<input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor's Degree
<input type="checkbox"/> Master's Degree	

Length of Service:

<input type="checkbox"/> more than 10 year	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 – 5 years
<input type="checkbox"/> 6 – 10 years	<input type="checkbox"/> less than 1 years

Part II. Assessment of the Teachers' Proficiency

Directions: Check the number which accurately corresponds to your assessment on the Teachers Competency and Learners Performance of Grade 2 Pupils based on the following scale.

OPTION	DESCRIPTIVE VALUE	NUMERICAL VALUE
5	Highly Competent	4.20 – 5.00
4	Competent	3.40 – 4.19
3	Moderately Competent	2.60 – 3.39
2	Least Competent	1.80 – 2.59
1	Not Competent	1.00 – 1.79

1.0 CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT	5	4	3	2	1
1.1. Manages classroom structure to engage learners in a meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within the range of physical learning environment.					
1.2. Manages learners' behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline.					
1.3. Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences					
1.4. Maintains safe and orderly classroom free from destructions.					
1.5. Establishes routines and procedures to maximize instructional time.					
2.0 MASTERY OF THE SUBJECTS	5	4	3	2	1
2.1. Uses appropriate pedagogy to achieve objectives of the lesson.					
2.2. Provides varied learning activities congruent with the objective of the lesson.					
2.3. Encourages interactive participation of the learners					
2.4. Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.					

2.5. Uses variety of teaching approaches and techniques appropriate to the learners and the subject matter.					
3.0 INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT	5	4	3	2	1
3.1. Develops instructional material aligned with the curriculum and subject area.					
3.2. Designs indigenous/ local instructional material for development.					
3.3. Provides activities and materials which fits the learners' learning style, goal and culture.					
3.4. Creates instructional material that reinforce application of concept and skills in real life situation.					
3.5. Constructs materials with varied enrichment activities to nurture the desire for further learning.					
4.0 TEACHING STRATEGIES AND APPROACHES	5	4	3	2	1
4.1. Uses appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT to address learning goals.					
4.2. Engages in mentoring with colleagues to improve teaching.					
4.3. Provides activities which address a range of learning styles/ multiple intelligences.					
4.4. Relates authentic learning experiences in a real-world context.					
4.5. Conducts action research in the classroom or school.					
5.0 COMMUNICATION SKILLS	5	4	3	2	1
5.1. Shows proficiency in the required language of instruction.					
5.2. Explains learning goals, concepts and processes clearly and accurately to the learners.					

5.3. Uses words appropriate for the pupils' level of understanding.					
5.4. Presents ideas clearly, logically and comprehensively.					
5.5. Uses expression to motivate and enhance learners' self-confidence.					
6.0 LEARNING ASSESSMENT AND REPORTING	5	4	3	2	1
6.1. Constructs valid and reliable formative and summative test.					
6.2. Uses appropriate non-traditional assessment techniques and tools (e.g. portfolio, journals, rubrics)					
6.3. Interprets and uses test results to improve teaching and learning.					
6.4. Keeps accurate records of grades performance levels of learners.					
6.5. Provides timely accurate feedback to learners to encourage them to reflect on and monitor their own learning growth.					
7.0 COMMUNITY LINKAGES					
7.1. Identifies various community resources available to enhance learning.					
7.2. Involves parents/ community in sharing accountability.					
7.3. Knows realities outside the classroom to make learning relevant.					
7.4. Informs learners, parents and other stakeholders regarding school policies and procedures.					
7.5. Recognizes the various activities, programs and projects where school-community partnerships are involved.					

Part III. Problems encountered by the teachers teaching Grade 2 learners

Directions: Below are some of the problem that you may encounter in teaching Grade 2 learners. Check the number which accurately corresponds to your answer.

OPTION	DESCRIPTIVE VALUE	NUMERICAL VALUE
5	Highly Encountered	4.20 – 5.00
4	Encountered	3.40 – 4.19
3	Moderately Encountered	2.60 – 3.39
2	Least Encountered	1.80 – 2.59
1	Not Encountered	1.00 – 1.79

PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED	5	4	3	2	1
1. Poor attendance and study habits of learners.					
2. Lack of skills and trainings.					
3. Lack of support from higher school officials.					
4. Lack of knowledge on the use of ICT.					
5. Lack of parents/community cooperation and support.					
6. Lack of textbooks and other instructional supplies.					
7. Lack of facilities for conducive teaching and learning process.					
8. Lack of sufficient time in teaching.					
9. Lack of learners' proper nutrition resulting to poor focus.					
10. Lack of learners' study habits.					

Thank you for spending your time in answering this questionnaire.